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Testing driver attention in virtual environments through audio cues

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Abstract

Virtual Reality has risen in popularity this decade due to the high level of interactive experience it provides to its users by encapsulating them in various computer-generated environments. These can range from video-games to real-life simulations where they try to create a near 3D experience similar to that one would have in the real world.

The introduction of audio on video-games or simulations can change not only the experience and feel of the environment but also improve the perception of their surroundings, including new elements otherwise not perceivable without audio. Human's audio attention process is complex and can change depending on the current context, time and depend on each personality, making it interesting to be studied.

This dissertation's main goal is to improve the agent's behaviour by creating an audio attention model to allow them to be aware of audio and react to the scenario's soundscape and to a specific event. By improving the agent's perceptions and actions, this makes their decision making better fit the virtual environment they are inserted. However, this requires studying the current scenario they belong to as well as the role they represent.

To create such attention model calls for the existence of audio on the current scenario. This led to the study of a city soundscape and its elements to comprehend what audio events exist and how relevant they are in that context. Then, it was necessary to fit this selection to the existent scenario and/or create new ways to use them without losing the realism level. Also, conventional audio output decoders do not fully represent on recreating the human auditory system due to its unique characteristics. 3D Audio and Binaural systems were introduced on the virtual space to better replicate the expected experience whilst immersed.

Afterwards, it was evaluated different ways on how to test audio attention on virtual environments and required studying research methods to do so. Human-Computer Interaction instructed on how to make applications more user-friendly and intuitive with the introduction of new modalities. Within-Subject design and Grounded theory proved to be useful in gathering data to use for the attention model, but this data provided limited usefulness due to the low number of participants and inconclusive in a lot of aspects, limiting the agent's audio attention model performance.

Lastly, there was implemented an approach to automatic audio classification by analysing the output signal mix and then with the results obtained, control the agent's perception by correctly or incorrectly identify the audio source and determine what the agent should do if the case. The usage of a Convolutional Neural Network with an embedded attention model was proposed to analyse the signal by evaluating it on a fully trained network, thanks to Google's audio dataset. Results were technically correct but were ambiguous on certain aspects and required some analysis to conclude what elements are present. This was also not viable due to how processing demanding it is and to other software constraints made obtaining results in real-time impossible. Explanations as to why this and other limitations happened and solutions were introduced to solve most problems on future interventions for related types of works.

Resumo

Realidade Virtual cresceu em popularidade nesta década devido ao alto nível de experiência interativa que fornece a seus utilizadores, encapsulando-os em vários ambientes gerados pelo computador. Estes podem variar de video-jogos para simulações da vida real, onde tentam criar uma experiência 3D semelhante à obtida no mundo real.

A introdução de áudio em video-jogos ou em simulações pode mudar não apenas a experiência e a sensação do ambiente, mas também melhorar a percepção de novos elementos que, de outra forma, não seriam detetados. O processo de atenção sonora é complexo e pode alterar dependendo do contexto atual, do tempo e da pessoa, tornando-se interessante de ser estudado.

O objetivo principal desta dissertação é de melhorar o comportamento de agentes através da criação de um modelo de atenção auditiva para que permita presenciar e reagir à paisagem sonora do cenário e a certos eventos sonoros. Ao melhorar as percepções e ações do agente, levará a que a sua tomada de decisão seja mais adequada ao ambiente virtual em que está inserido. No entanto, isso requer estudar o cenário atual a qual pertencem e o papel que eles representam.

Para criar esse modelo de atenção requer a presença de áudio no cenário atual. Para tal, foi necessário um estudo da paisagem sonora de cidades e quais os seus elementos para compreender que eventos de áudio existem e quão relevantes estes são. De seguida, foi necessário adequar esta seleção ao cenário existente e criar novas formas de usá-las sem perder o nível de realismo. Além disso, os decodificadores de saída de áudio convencionais não representam totalmente a recriação do sistema auditivo humano devido às suas características. 3D Audio e Binaural foram introduzidos no espaço virtual para melhor replicar a experiência expectável enquanto imerso.

Posteriormente, foram avaliadas diferentes formas de testar a atenção auditiva em ambientes virtuais e de métodos necessários de pesquisa para tal. Interação Computador Humano instruiu sobre como fazer aplicações mais fáceis de usar e intuitivas, com a introdução de novas modalidades, neste caso som. *Within Subject Design* e *Grounded Theory* provaram ser úteis na recolha de dados para utilizar no modelo de atenção. No entanto, esses dados provaram ser limitados devido ao baixo número de participantes e de serem inconclusivos em muitos aspectos, limitando a performance do modelo de atenção de áudio.

Por fim, foi implementada uma abordagem de classificação automática de áudio, que visa a analisar a mistura de sinal de saída e, em seguida, com os resultados obtidos, controlar a percepção do agente através da correta ou incorreta identificação da fonte de áudio e determinar o que o agente deva fazer. O uso de uma Rede Neural Convolutiva com um modelo de atenção incorporado foi proposto para analisar o sinal, avaliando-o numa rede totalmente ligada e treinada, graças ao conjunto de dados de áudio da Google. Os resultados foram tecnicamente corretos, mas ambíguos em certos aspectos e exigiam algumas análises para concluir quais elementos estão presentes. Mostrou-se também não ser viável devido à alta exigência de processamento e a outras restrições de software que tornaram impossível a obtenção de resultados em tempo real. Explicações e soluções sobre porquê desta e de outras limitações foram introduzidas para solucionar a maioria destes problemas em intervenções futuras para tipos de trabalhos relacionados.

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Hasta la vista FEUP.

João Loureiro aka Jonas

*“There is no first
we get it and that’s it.”*

Bruce Greene

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Abbreviations

2D	Two Dimensional
3D	Three Dimensional
AI	Artificial Intelligence
APP	Application
CNN	Convolutional Neural Networks
DNN	Deep Neural Networks
HCI	Human-Computer Interaction
HRTF	Head-Related Transfer Function
MAS	Multi-Agent System
MIL	Multiple Instance Learning
ML	Machine Learning
MMHCI	MultiModal Human-Computer Interaction
NN	Neural Networks
NPC	Non-Playable Character
QQ	Questionnaire Question
RQ	Research Question
VR	Virtual Reality
VE	Virtual Environment
WWW	<i>World Wide Web</i>

Chapter 1

Introduction

Virtual Reality (VR) [SS17] is a human-machine interaction scientific technology for understanding and simulating the real or virtual environment (VE) into a 3D space much similar to that of a real-life scenario and experiencing the same natural physical presence and feeling one would on the real world by emerging the users into a simulated environment using computers or even mobile smartphones along with sensory equipment like headsets and/or gloves [SS17]. This has suffered a huge development over the recent years [MG99] [CH17] and not only did it improve its level of immersion and software/hardware performances, but it also increased the number of devices capable of handling this technology. Plus, it boosted the level of interest by the general public, as well as the investment in this area to expand its compatibility with other areas such as Artificial Intelligence (AI).

This can be used as an upgrade for Video-Games or Simulations due to the immersive, multi-sensory experience [MG99] it brings compared to the limited interaction capabilities of the existing computer or mobile applications with its users. To date, VR applications focus more on two of the Human senses: the visual and auditory sense, being this last one the main target of interest of this dissertation. One of the main focus of all the work to be done is to evaluate its importance on VR apps and the interaction between the user and the VE.

Despite of having the possibility to recreate realistic acoustic effects in a VE [Dei+07] [Vor+15] such like the reverberation and reflection of sound in rooms or in open scenarios, one of the goals of this dissertation is to simulate a basic and realistic sound perception of a VE as for a user perspective by using 3D Sound Spatialization [Cor17] and Binaural Audio [Wal17] [Vor+15] in order to fulfil this immersive experience.

However, another interesting approach can be taken relative to the Human experience regarding audio. This involves emulating human interaction with audio. First, the sonorization process must be as close as possible to reality in order to keep the level of realism and immersion of the User. Next, the behaviour of the NPCs present in the VR scene is necessary to look upon as to not only increase the VR experience and user interaction, but also replicate Human behaviour to

study different case scenarios and evaluate the level of utility and presence sound has on people on their daily basis. Especially for simulations whose goal is to have an easier perception of data or natural phenomena appearance/occurrence. Simulations have already a high presence [MG99] for educational and studies purposes in VR as you can better replicate real-life situations and test new case scenarios to implement into real life in case the results are what to be expected.

On the following sections of the Introduction chapter, it further develops this dissertation's context, motivation, objectives as well as the document structure to better understand this work's goal.

1.1 Context

This dissertation further develops on a previous work done in Unity VR. This revolves around a 3D city environment whose focal point is to recreate all actions that happen on a regular city scenario which can be visual aspects with the presence on the environment of physical objects such as buildings, roads, sidewalks, semaphores and vehicles as well as human-being representations either as pedestrians or as drivers. Then, in order to fully recreate a city experience, it was necessary to introduce autonomous agents to inhabit the VE and to behave accordingly to what a human would do, turning the Virtual Reality system into a simulation scenario. Each agent has a specific behaviour depending on the role it is performing, the timing and context of the situation. So a pedestrian agent will have similar actions on the same scenarios like walking on an empty sidewalk but it differs on a different situation like crossing a crosswalk with or without nearby cars.

On the previous work done by António Casimiro *et al* [Cas18] the main goal was to test and model visual attention to the simulation agents in order to improve their behaviour as to prove that humans have different visual attention and perception in certain case scenarios involving different sets of city events and contexts as for looking into specific or most relevant object of the situation. This was done by studying visual attention models and by studying with an eye tracker to receive data on specific scenarios on the existent VE. However, this came in as inconclusive as either the proposed model or validation method for the data were incorrectly chosen.

This dissertation main goal is to focus on the audio aspect of the city and the importance it might have to the realism of the simulation, as well as the impact it has on the user's behaviour. Not only that but it is necessary to introduce and teach the concept of audio to the agents so they can also interact with the current audio available on the simulation. Therefore it is necessary to model the perception of audio as well as attention to rank different sounds with different degrees of relevance to the context.

In order to do so, it is necessary to look at how Humans perceive, distinguish and locate sound. Next, explore sound in an environment in its complexity, ambivalence, meaning and context and, for this case, target specifically for city environments by studying Soundscape. Despite some of the sound characteristics such as intensity being physically measured, it is important to note that the perception and evaluation of sound must have a holistic approach as it is something that

cannot be quantified and can change depending on several factors like the person/user in question and context.

It is also mandatory to look up at the current state of the art of available audio attention models and classification algorithms [Xu+15] [Sto+15] and their current limitations. Google's *et al* [Her+17] approach made possible of a creation of an audio dataset [Aud19b] which created the possibility to have more accurate projects and approaches for acoustic event detection [Pan17] [KR17] and integration attention models to improve it [Kon+18] [Yu+18].

As so, to reach the goal of modelling audio attention and perception it is necessary to contextualise the auditory environment adequate to the existing city environment by studying what elements exist on a city, what kind of sounds happen on it, select the most relevant events people listen to daily and then analyse the data retrieved to implement them onto the simulation by sonorizing the objects on the scene to try and recreate the same environment in VR. After that, it is important to study the impact of specific audio events on human attention as to implement such information on the attention model and finally, the agents must perceive and identify different components on a real-time audio signal, which they receive throughout the execution of the simulation.

1.2 Motivation and Objectives

This dissertation's main goal is to prove the usefulness of audio in realistic scenarios such as on the VE already mentioned as to complement the visual aspect of the applications and to correctly cause an expected behaviour on its users, just like they would do on their daily basis. For this particular case, one recent question emerged with the risen popularity of electric cars, is the need for sound for it to be noticeable by pedestrians. With this dissertation, it will be possible to test the impact of the presence/absence of audio during the city experience, by having specific triggerable events to check the human response to it or to check if the attention levels for one particular audio clip can change, depending on a different scenario. This, however, requires the existence of said audio events.

To provide a realistic experience to the user, it is mandatory to study what elements exist in the available context. Since this is inserted in a city scenario, this leads to the study of its soundscape as to determine what is required to sonorize. After this, the perception of the implemented solution might differ to what is expected in real-life due to the sheer complexity of the human anatomy. Studies regarding human auditory system and how to solve said problems will be done to further improve the user's experience.

Then, it is important to integrate the obtained results on the simulation's agents to increase their knowledge of the world and improve their interaction with the VE. This leads to the implementation of an Audio Attention Model where the agents are able to properly distinguish different playable audio clips during the simulation and to properly evaluate them based on the level of relevance they have. Initially, it only is able to differentiate them by checking their label and later on it will be based on the current audio signal the agents can capture on their audible radius, which

introduces the need of having a proper way of doing so. One of the proposed solutions is using a trained convolutional neural network with an adequate data set for this scenario which can automatically label different audio clips present at a given time on the simulation. All of this happens within a city environment context which cannot be directly used on other daily activities.

Since the information obtained is subjective to the user experience and actions, to further analyse the proposed methods it is important to do a research to test the solution implemented. This will be interesting as it is needed to prepare the research and by receiving feedback and data from the users also serves as validation which is necessary for the models to be functioning as expected. Human-Computer Interaction provides a selection of methods and instructions to prepare and customise researches to collect valid useful data to reach our desired objective.

This work can contribute as an example for other activities where sound plays a big role in the human interaction with the environment he is in and there is a need to properly simulate his behaviour on a specific case scenario using Multi-Agent systems. This is not only restricted to simulations but can be interesting also on video games to increase the player's interaction with NPCs or other interactive events on the game.

1.3 Dissertation Structure

In addition to the introduction, this document also contains four more chapters, Literature Review, Methodological Approach, "Experiment, Results and Discussion" and Conclusions and Future work. The chapter Literature Review presents the current state of the art of topics related to this dissertation development, as well as some previous projects as research to draw a comparison between their goals and main points to this dissertation's objectives. The literature review will focus on three main topics of investigation, each with its fields of research:

- Sound and Human Hearing System
 - General Approach to audio. (explain the concepts of sound, audio), as well as some psychoacoustic features and concepts such as sound recognition, perception and localisation.
 - introduce and explain more technical concepts such as Soundscapes, 3D Sound Spatialization, Audio Binaural
- Multi-Agent System
 - General description about what is Multi-Agent Systems, usability and goals. Describe types of agents and define what is going to be used.
 - Attention and Behaviour Models. General description of audio and basic models. Introduction to an audio attention model
 - Neural Networks. Explain different neural network concepts as well as introduction to already implemented/used networks in previous works.

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- Human-Computer Interaction
 - General description about what is Human-Computer Interaction, usability and goals. Explain utility relative to the human experience with computer apps as well as VR experience.
 - Multimodal Interaction to justify the use as a complement to the visual aspect of the Virtual Reality Simulation
 - Research methods to collect data to use to validate the usefulness and importance of audio on the simulation using quantitative and qualitative methods such as Within-subject, Between-group subject design methods as well as Grounded theory to further.

The chapter Methodological Approach introduces the structure of the existent project and proposes a solution to this work main problem according to the information and content provided in the previous chapter. This is organised into three different parts:

- Audio Processing.
 - Current Context is introduced to understand what city components are more relevant for the user experience, as well as analysing the current Unity environment to identify similarities and differences of a real city.
 - Audio Event Selection after previous discussion to filter what elements are to be sonorized and list various audio events to be implemented on the VE.
 - Audio Creation, Tweaking and Integration to explain the audio creation and manipulation techniques used along with its implementation in Unity. This also explains the necessary arrangements done for integrating 3D Audio.
- Research Study. This is for preparing the questionnaire to be done further into the dissertation's work. This evolves selecting the appropriate research methods and questions in order to gather valid opinions and data for future usage.
- Audio Classification and Attention Model. It is presented an approach for a system architecture evolving the integration of both proposed models and how they should work and interact with Unity to complement its agent's information of the available events and what behaviour they should have by only providing a single audio signal output.

The chapter Experiment, Results and Discussion details how the planned work was executed, specifically the user experiment and questionnaire, the outcomes of said experience and what the results correspond to the actual behaviour the users had. This was structured according to the chronological execution of said actions. First, the necessary scenario arrangements were required for gathering the necessary material for the experiment, as well as creating new audio sources not available on the Unity scene. Then, the test setup was conducted to prepare all scripted events to be tested throughout the experiment, according to what was prepared on the research study

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subsection. After that, it was established an experimental protocol to pinpoint every mandatory step executed during each experiment to guarantee the same controlled experience is repeated and to not corrupt or influence any obtained data. Results and discussion of said data were followed as to analyse it and evaluate the overall impact audio had on the Unity scene. Each question was looked upon on as to explain the individual results obtained and at the end, a final summary was presented to conclude if the previous discussed approaches and assumptions were correct or if something different or unexpected was achieved. Lastly, it is discussed on how the classification and attention models were implemented and what limitations were brought by the data gathered on the previous steps and by the proposed architecture, which lead to some changes on this process.

The last chapter resumes all previous work and approaches discussed into final conclusions about the contribution of all selected fields of study. This included explaining the impact and importance of audio for object perception and VR experience to improve the realism levels. An evaluation of the proposed methods (HCI research methods used, audio classification and attention models) and their usefulness was conducted to check if they are viable or not for the current context. To better improve this work and to fix any problems that appeared during this dissertation's work, which can happen in future projects, suggestions and proposals for solutions were given based on the observations, studies and results collected available on this document.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

This chapter will focus on the current state of the art and previous work related to what it is necessary in order to understand the different fields of work needed to develop a solution to this dissertation main goal and main objectives.

For this dissertation, there are three different and distinct areas chosen, each with different applications for this work. Sound and Human Hearing System is related to sound characteristics, the human physical condition and restrictions to sound waves, 3D audio and binaural audio and how this can reduce the human perception error. Multi-Agent system topic will elaborate on how different agents behave with each other and with events that happen on the VE and methods that will be responsible for building or changing attention and perception models for the agents. Lastly, there is Human-Computer Interaction which will be responsible for emphasising the importance of audio in VE and realistic simulations relatively to the interaction with its users and also on how to do research methods to validate said interaction and also to test new case scenarios relative to the interaction with audio events.

The following study of the state of the art will be an important investigation for the Methodological Approach as this will be the foundation for the methods later on applied and decisions made during this dissertation's work.

2.1 Sound and Human Hearing System

Sound, audio, and noise, although often used as interchangeable terms, have specific definitions and meaning. Sound is a form of energy which is propagated by pressure variations as a wave on surrounding medium (solid, liquid or gas such as the air) and it is originated by vibrations of a single or multiple objects [Pla05] [Moo03]. Sound waves are the physical elements humans can detect and perceive using the brain [Moo03]. Audio or Audio Signal is the electrical representation of sound. Audio signals can be synthesised or originated using transducers. These are elements of the microphone which are responsible for detecting and converting sound waves to an

audio signal. Noise, from a perception standpoint, is any unwanted or out-of-context sound which can be disruptive to the human hearing [F C52].

To understand how the human being captures sound waves using its hearing system, following the conversion of said sound waves to "perceivable" sound by humans and finally the neural processes of manipulating the captured sound in the brain, it is necessary to check Psychoacoustics as it is the field of study which further develops the understanding of these processes.

2.1.1 Psychoacoustics

Psychoacoustics is the behavioural study of hearing, in which conscious listeners are required to make perceptual decisions regarding the sounds that are played to them [Pla05]. This may range from distinguishing frequency changes and prioritising certain frequencies [Moo03], intensity variations and also the location of sound. Despite sound being a physical representation in a form of a wave, the problem begins with the perception humans experience when it listens to a particular set of sounds and then it is processed after entering our ears by being converted into electrical activity in neurons of the auditory nerve. After that, it is also necessary to look upon the human restrictions to sound as our perception of certain elements of sound such as Pitch and loudness as they do not change linearly based on the sound wave characteristics such as altitude and frequency.

First and to help illustrate how sound starts to be processed by the human hearing system it is important to observe the anatomy of the human hearing. All of the following information will be based on Christopher J. Plack *et al* [Pla05]

Figure 2.1: Anatomy of the human ear [Pla05]

The Pinna is what it is popularly called of ear and acts as an auxiliary member part of the hearing system, whose goal is to localise sounds by modifying sound waves based on the direction of the sound source [Moo03]. The part that is physically responsible for the "hearing process" begins on the ear canal, which acts as an entrance to the sound waves and ends on the eardrum. The ear canal provides a resonance effect that is sensitive to sound frequencies ranging from 1000

to 6000 Hz. The eardrum is a membrane that vibrates when sound waves reach it. This vibration depends on the intensity of the sound, increasing the amplitude of the vibration according to how much the intensity is, having a threshold for maximum and minimum value, which will be analysed later on this section. Then, the vibrations are carried through the Malleus, Incus, and Stapes (three smallest bones of the human body). The Stapes is connected to another membrane named Cochlea, which is a narrow fluid-filled tube. This is where the pressure variations are converted into electrical activity perceived by the neurons of the auditory nerve, which basically translates the acoustic information into the language of the brain [Pla05].

Figure 2.2: Frequency variation along the basilar membrane [Pla05]

On the Cochlea is the basilar membrane, which presents a spiral form. When there exists pressure variations on the Cochlea, these will cause the basilar membrane to vibrate up and down. These vibrate in specific places depending on different characteristic frequencies, which can be observed in the previous image. So at the base of the Cochlea is most sensitive to high-frequency pure-tone components and near the apex is most sensitive to low-frequency components, being the maximum frequency listenable of roughly 20 000 Hz and the minimum 20 Hz. So it is possible to conclude that each place on the basilar membrane acts as an auditory filter being selective to a range of frequencies [Moo03].

The main function of the basilar membrane is to separate complex sound waves (which essentially are a combination of pure-tone components) into individual harmonics. This is an essential step in the perception of sound as it is identified mostly by their spectra and by its variation over time. So the membrane is able to distinguish differences in frequency composition from different sounds, which makes them identifiable. However, there is a problem that is brought from this. When pure tones have similar frequencies, it becomes hard to distinguish the quieter one, since the more intense one will *mask* the other one due to creating more vibration on that area and creates a masking effect [Moo03]. The opposite happens when tones have different frequencies as it will make it easier to hear the weaker sound. The masking effect brings a selectivity problem on listening to certain sounds, creating a frequency selectivity problem. This was measured by experiments on humans with different sounds and the results can be seen on the following image, regarding the master level needed to mask a 4000 Hz pure tone [Pla05].

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Figure 2.3: Level variation of intensity needed for a given frequency to mask a 4000 Hz pure tone. [Pla05]

As for intensity perception, there are also some problems in creating a relation between intensity and loudness perceived. Loudness is the subjective magnitude of a sound and not the physical property of the sound since there is no linear formula to convert loudness to intensity [Pla05]. As seen in figure 2.4, the graph represents how the loudness perceived evolves with different levels of intensity.

Figure 2.4: Loudness level (sones) by Intensity level (dB SPL) [Pla05]

It becomes clear that at some levels it is difficult to distinguish the variation of intensity. This also becomes harder to detect at higher levels of intensity, especially at 110 dB when auditory-nerve neurons become over saturated.

Lastly, there is the problem of Sound Localisation. As already mentioned, the direction of a sound is determined by the differences of the sound signals at the eardrums. However, having two ears helps humans to locate the direction of a sound source to some level. There are two main

cues, being Interaural time differences (sound to the right arrives at the right ear before the left ear) and Interaural level difference (sound to the right is more intense in the right ear) [Pla05].

Interaural time differences are essential for sound localisation due to the high level of the ears sensitivity in detecting audio, which can distinguish the arrival of a sound to both ears within a very small time difference, which represent the direction angle of the sound source [Moo03]. The difference would be zero if the sound came from straight ahead or from the back. The tone frequency is also responsible for the different perception of the sound signals in both ears, changing the distance between waveform peaks. For a continuous pure tone coming directly to the right, a waveform peak in the left ear will be closely followed by a peak in the right ear [Moo03]. This will create an ambiguity as the sound source will seem to be originated from the left when, in fact, is coming from the right. This can be resolved if the waveform envelope fluctuates so that the more slowly varying features can be compared. In general, however, interaural time differences are more important at low frequencies [Pla05].

In contrast, interaural level differences are more useful at high frequencies. The head will tend to prevent the sound waves from reaching the ear furthest from the sound, creating an acoustic shadow effect and leading to large level differences between the ears. However, at low frequencies, the sound can bend round or diffract around the head so that the level differences are not impactful [Pla05].

There are studies which proved how in fact humans managed to perceive sound [Bla69]. However, this is hard to replicate due to the complexity of the physical human anatomy, and even harder without having to rely on visual cues, being hard to recreate a fully realistic sound perception system. However, as it will be possible to conclude on the 3D Audio subsection, there are already approaches for VR to simulate Sound Spatialization which is statistically proven to be realistic [Hon16].

2.1.2 Soundscapes

Soundscape [Sch77] is a collection of sounds that resemble or try to resemble a specific immersive environment [M B+14]. This will create the sensation of experiencing an acoustic environment or composition using the recorded sounds. This is not restricted only to physical ambients but also abstract constructions such as musical compositions and tape montages. Soundscapes focus on every acoustic event that can happen to range from natural events such as the weather to sounds created by humans like walking or talking and also ranges to sounds with mechanical or industrial origin such as car engines or construction sites. According to R. Murray Schafer *et al* [Sch77] one can classify the sound objects inside of a soundscape in 6 different categories:

1. Natural sounds: water, air, animals, and others.
2. Human sounds: body movement, talking, clothes.
3. Sounds and Society: rural/city soundscapes, factory/professions, entertainment like music, parks or gardens for example.

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4. Mechanical Sounds: machines, factory equipment, etc.
5. Quiet and Silence.
6. Sound as Indicators: bells, horns, cellphones, sirens.

Besides categorising by type of sound object, Schafer also categorised by the impact one sound has on the current acoustic environment. This is divided into three different types of sounds, being the first one Keynote Sounds which are considered as background continuous sounds like the sea waves on a beach, then Signal Sounds which contrasts with Keynote as it specifically directs people's attention towards an object or location and lastly there is Soundmarks which sounds that are unique or have a quality that is remarkable within the local environment.

Soundscapes can also play a big role in VR as not only to provide an immersive experience but also as a way of navigation and helping identifying elements present on the current scene, especially with the introduction of Soundmarks [CYD15]. This can also be justifiable by the introduction of an extra modality (auditory) which will be explained later on the sub-chapter 2.3.1.

The soundscape experience is not always constant and can change depending on the current location and the current events happening at a given time. And, as mentioned in the last paragraph, some sounds have more relevance in terms of human attention rather than others. This field of study is interesting as it allows the analysis of the impact and interaction of an acoustic environment as with the people who inhabit or frequently go on said place. For this work, it is necessary to study City Soundscapes in order to comprehend and study what sounds exist in such place in order to implement/populate them on the already existent VE with the purpose of not only give the correct ambience experience with the users but also to be able to recreate certain scenarios and to study interactions between them and its users.

The study of City Soundscapes has been done for some time now and more recently for the same reasons mentioned above: some focus [Sou69] on what are the sound elements present on the city and the sonic identity by analysing different places and gathering data from recordings or by interviewing people; others [Sou67] focus on doing experiments with a wide range of people on the interaction between various daily basis scenarios to check the impact of different sound events and testing different hypothesis. Finally, others [M B+14] focus on how to study City Soundscapes and how to properly do both types of researches mentioned before.

The above mentioned research papers will be useful for this dissertation to sonorize the VE creating a proper atmosphere to increase the realism of the simulation and to also be able to create the possibility of testing different interactions in order to understand and gather data for developing an attention and behaviour model for this simulation environment. In [Sou69] there was conducted a study to analyse the variety and frequency of certain sounds experienced by the pedestrians who lived in a large city, being this study case Boston. The following image is the results obtained.

Figure 2.5: Subject Inquiry about the Soundscape of Boston. [Sou69]

This can give a general idea of what sounds exist in cities and what influence these have over the people who have to face them on a daily basis. Dashed lines represent visual and auditory stimuli while the clean only represents auditory stimuli. While some events are completely identifiable by visual aid, most events are mentioned by most part by only require listening to them, which proves that audio does play a big role in guiding people. Traffic is by far the most mentioned as one could guess since Boston has over six hundred thousand inhabitants and generates a lot of movement inside the city. This then plays a big role in order to reconstruct a City Soundscape.

2.1.3 3D Audio and Binaural System

3D Audio is a digital proposed replica of the hearing sensation humans have by giving the notion of complete control and manipulation of the user's spatial auditory perception [Beg00]. This allows the user to be able to identify sounds in all orientations possible, being them azimuth and elevation, as well as the distance determined sound is emitted. The Figure 2.6 is a visual representation of the concepts mentioned before. The Environmental Context mentioned on the figure is the audio content that identifies the elements of a determined scene. This will be a part of the Soundscape study of this dissertation 2.1.2 and will be later on implemented and discussed.

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Figure 2.6: Spatial Auditory Perception Taxonomy [Beg00]

The technical innovation that enables the advances proposed in 3-D Audio over traditional stereo is the use of signal processing to superimpose directionally dependent transfer functions on the stereo output signals. These functions must recreate the complex acoustic cues used by listeners on their daily basis to determine the location of a sound source in 3D space [Ken11]. A Spatial Audio model which takes advantages of these technology improvements and is able to recreate realistically the perception of sound in a 3D world is Binaural Technology.

Binaural technology represents an alternative of the conventional stereo audio reproduction, allowing the subjectively accurate 3D representation of sound through the usage of two loudspeakers or headphones [TF07]. This achieves 3D audio environment recreation by synthesising a two-channel audio signal using Head Related Transfer Functions (HRTF) between the sound source and each listener's human ear. Thus, only two loudspeakers or headphones are required for binaural audio playback [TF07]. Since the technology required for reproducing sound is very accessible, as headphones are widely used worldwide, and due to the advantages binaural systems bring over stereo for a higher realism level and overall listening experience, this is becoming increasingly pursued in systems like VR [Wal17] due to the increasing demand of the search in simulating reality.

There already exists audio software capable of encoding existent audio to be binaural ready. Reaper [Rea19] is a digital audio workstation that can manipulate, tweak and synthesise audio and encode it to any desired type, being one of them to binaural. It is then possible to not only manipulate audio by just changing the encoding, but it is also available to change its source of location which automatically manipulates the audio signal to give the perception of a certain location. To integrate audio onto Unity and manage inside the location and objects it should sonorize there is middleware software like Wwise [Aud19a] and FMOD [Fir19]. Both of these also have capabilities of audio editing, as well as plugins, like the Resonance Audio [Goo19] which allow the addition of binaural effects to the existing audio events present on the scene.

2.2 Multi-Agent System

Simulation [AS07] consists of a set of rules that manage how a system will develop during a certain amount of time, depending on a set of conditions the state of the system at the time has. Most of the time, due to the complexity of the real world, the simulation's objective is not to accurately represent scenarios but act as an approximation of the expected behaviour and can be restricted to only a limited set of actions. This allows for more simplification and abstraction of a real-life event and help analysing and to study more relevant characteristics in order to create new theories based on the predictions observed in the simulation. One approach for simulations within an investigation or research area [MF14] is the usage of Multi-Agent Systems as it is not only popular for this type of work but also it is adequate relative to the real-life problem that this dissertation is trying to replicate.

Multi-Agent Systems [DKJ18] are a kind of system which contains more than one type of autonomous entities known as agents. These are able to [DMF09] interact with the involving environment, are driven by a set of goals or objectives, have their own state, have knowledge of their current space and interact with other agents. Agents can have two types of architecture, the first one is a Reactive Architecture which restricts the agent behaviour strictly to response of stimuli received from other agents and the second one is Cognitive Architecture which considers that agents reason from knowledge which can be obtained *a priori* or by interaction with agents or the current environment state [DMF09]. One type of this architecture is Belief-Desire-Intention (BDI) architecture that takes previous information and observed information and takes decisions based on this and what they want to achieve which resembles the most human-like type of way of acting. As for this work, the architecture adopted by this simulation environment agents will look more like a Cognitive Architecture. Besides most of the interactions being interacting with other agent's audio stimuli, it requires knowledge of the environment and beliefs/prior knowledge for the agent to properly behave according to a human.

For the agents to act like humans when regarding audio stimuli there surges the need process audio in different parts: detect audio events, perception, and classification of different audio clips, attention level and reaction to different audio stimuli.

Previous work on using simulated environments or games for behaviour elicitation have been made with promising results [Ram+17; Alm+14]. These can be used as a basis for agent modelling or for highlighting areas where humans may require assistance, such as in a driving scenario [Gon+15; Gon+14].

2.2.1 Audio Classification and Neural Networks

Audio Perception is the ability humans have to understand and identify the presence of a determined existence of specific events that are captured on an audio signal. Audio Classification is a computer method whose goal is to label what events can be detected on determined audio signals. There are multiple methods of implementing a functional and effective classification for audio [Pan17] [Sto+15] [KR17], however these all rely on one important detail. In order for a program

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to know what sound is, it needs a source of information to learn what different audio labels exist and how they look like to be able to compare to others. This first requires some sort of training using labeled audio data, or as it is commonly called an audio dataset.

A dataset is an organised source of the same type of information, similar to a library, which was created either manually or by using automatic computational methods. This usually has a considerable amount of entries to be more valid and reliable as a source of information and presents different types of variables depending on the type of data. For example, images usually are represented as 3x3 RGB matrixes and a label which identifies what element is visible on the image or instead can simply present the average values of each RGB component. For audio datasets there exists one problem, which is the complexity of creating a high dimension valid dataset using automatic methods, since it is hard to accurately label audio events just by signal processing and require multiple methods to complement it like analysing manual human descriptions and visual signal processing for object detecting and confirming the sound source. This was done by Google *et al* [Aud19b] using Youtube's videos to classify the audio captured on each of them using video processing to detect the scene's objects, audio signal processing and user's video description [Her+17]. However, this has produced weakly labeled data due to the lack of detailed information available to categorise audio events, which is one problem for audio datasets. Some of these problems include the time of the event, number of times the event happened and its duration. One proposed project improved Google's audio dataset by analysing and structuring the audio information into a parent tree of categories to better detail the audio classification [Gem+17].

Now that it is clear what kind of data is used for Audio Classification, it is necessary to check the different methods available to accurately audio labeling/detection. One approach for detection and classification of acoustic events consisted purely of the creation of signal processing methods and the creation of an own audio dataset [Sto+15]. Most of the other approaches studied all take advantage of Google's Audio dataset using Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning methods. One of them uses exactly this with Tensor Flow which has built-in Machine Learning methods required to predict audio tagging [Pan17]. Others use an Audio Classification approach Multiple Instance Learning (MIL) and Neural Networks [KR17] [Her+17] [Kon+18].

Neural Networks (NN) is an approach to simulate the human brain in terms of learning and pattern recognition based on what was learnt. NN consists of many simple connected neurons, which can be classified as three types: input, processing (neurons present on the hidden layers of the Neural Network) and output [Ram+15]. Input neurons get activated through the initial real-life data that is provided into them. Then, it passes to the next hidden layer of the network and activates processing neurons. These have weighted connections attached to the previous neurons of the layer and will update the values from the previous ones. This will last until it reaches the final layer which is where the output neurons are located [Ram+15]. The final values presented by these are what are then used to compare to distinguish between different input values to test their similarity. To update the weighted connections to make the Neural Network converge to correct results it is necessary to integrate a learning methodology. One efficient way is the application of a gradient descent method for Supervised Learning in discrete, differentiable networks of any depth

called backpropagation. This works especially well for Neural Networks with multiple layers called Deep Neural Networks (DNN) as it increases the overall performance of it [Ram+15] and can also be adopted for Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN). CNN or convnets is a different type of Neural Network, it still maintains the same process of updateable weights and biases but presents a different architecture. The previous NN mentioned are introduced with 2D data (each input presents a set of variables) while CNN can manage 3D data on their input (width, height, depth). This requires also a restructure on the CNN hidden layer, where it is introduced with new layer types, being the Convolutional Layer responsible for computing the output of neurons that are connected to local regions in the previous input, each computing a dot product between their weights and a small region they are connected to in the input volume, and the Subsampling Layers which will perform downsampling operations on their input, simplifying data along the depth of the CNN [Ram+15]. CNN are useful for more heavyweight and complex data such as images and audio, whose representation is difficult to represent in a 2D format. As for the learning methodology necessary for the CNN and audio detection and classification, it is necessary to look into MIL.

Multiple Instance Learning (MIL) is a learning methodology that relies on the labels of a group of instances, rather than labels of individual ones. This is often described in terms of bags (collection of instances). When needed to detect the presence of an element there are two possible classifications: positive bag which has at least one match and negative bag which contains zero instances [KR17]. This is very useful for audio detection as the approach is very theoretically very similar. MIL is used in adapted NN in order to train them for this particular case. Regarding audio, it is necessary to adapt MIL into a NN that presents an architecture useful for audio data, which is CNN. There already exists CNN adapted with MIL for training purposes [KR17] [Her+17] [Kon+18] and both present good statistical power on their Audio Classification proposal. While the Anurag Kumar and Bhiksha Raj's work *et al* [KR17] only uses the assistance of ML methods like MIL and Backpropagation, Google's [Her+17] use the assistance of human descriptions and CNN for visual analysis to better the overall performance. Finally, the last proposed work had an approach of trying to simulate an Attention Model which managed to improve the results obtained by Google's proposed CNN Acoustic event detection and classification [Kon+18].

2.2.2 Attention and Audio Attention Model

Attention is a difficult concept to describe despite everyone knowing what it has William James *et al* [Jam10] stated. According to him, attention is transcending the mind in order to focus on objects or trains of thought. He defends that focalization, concentration, and consciousness are their essence and imply that it is necessary to focus on one aspect and ignoring the rest, introducing the problems of confusion, dazzling and distraction. This can be considered somewhat true if we categorise attention into different categories as Sohberg and Mateer *et al* [Soh01] did base on the cognitive resources the brain provides. Such can be focused attention, selectivity, and divided attention. For audio attention, this is also a problem to manage how this is processed by the human brain. One well-known problem regarding audio attention is the cocktail party effect [Bro15]

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which is the ability to focus on one or more particular sound sources and blurring the other ones, acting as a selective filter for one element while ignoring others.

To replicate this problem and try to model attention for computer usage to further test, predict and understand how the human mind works, there was the need to implement attention models target specifically for a determined problem. For the example mentioned before, there is already an approach to implement an attention model with the intent to recreate the cocktail effect [Xu+15].

Audio Attention Models were also introduced on one of the Audio Classification approaches done by Qiuqiang Kong, Yong Xu, Wenwu Wang and Mark D. Plumbley *et al* [Kon+18] mentioned in the previous subsection. This uses a proposed attention model which was later on updated to a multi-level attention model proposed by Changsong Yu, Bin Yang and again Qiuqiang Kong *et al* [Yu+18]. This model uses DNN to focus on the relevant instances existing on a bag and ignore the others. This is useful as to ignore some minor audio signal which can be considered as inaudible for humans and irrelevant to that moment for the scene such as background noise.

The proposed single-level attention model proposed by Qiuqiang Kong *et al* [Kon+18] uses a probabilistic approach, more specifically a weighted collective assumption which tries to update the weight of relevance/impact of an instance of a bag. While the previous attention model applied only at the output of the CNN, the multi-level attention model is applied after intermediate layers as well [Yu+18]. The images on the Figure 2.7 represent both types of architecture. Practically, the difference between both modules is that the single-level calculates prediction based on one Equation [Yu+18] [Kon+18] while multi-level applies the same formula to different intermediate layer levels and concatenates them on a vector at the output, To finish the process a sigmoid non-linearity function is applied to obtain the final result. The performance of the multi-level attention model is superior to the single-level and Google's CNN results since multi-level features extracted from the intermediate layers provide various representations, and then each attention module can filter the unrelated information of each feature. Besides, different classes may favor different layer of features and the last fully connected layer of each multi-level attention model can automatically select the best feature for each class by the weight parameters [Yu+18].

Figure 2.7: Architecture of the single and multi-level attention model [Yu+18]

2.3 Human-Computer Interaction

Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) [SSS10] [BK18] is the field of study which researches the relation between a human and a computer to understand how to improve the usability and functionality of the design in order to create a more interactive and functional computer system for a specific usage and for a specific target. The main goal of HCI is to get to a consensus of the user needs and perceptions and the system design in order to be more user-friendly while not losing the main purpose of the system, so it still has its core functions. This is not an exact science [BK18] as most of the interactions between humans change based on certain points such as age, level of expertise with interfaces, apps and technology, knowledge and physical conditions which might impair some basic actions. These limitations will dictate how one person responsible for improving the system's interaction can update or add new content to be more useful for its users. There are some options one can decide in order to better check on how to introduce to these improvements, one of them being already established conventions which will improve the interaction between the general group of people and another one which will be explored next is research methods. These will look into more detail for either a specific problem and/or specific target people and gather information about what it is needed to be investigated and improved. For this dissertation, the first point to prove is why the introduction of audio on an already existent system/environment will help humans interact with it and the second one is the introduction of two/three research methods that will help validate and/or change any missing key points on the VE.

2.3.1 MultiModal Interaction

With the advance in technology in the recent years, it was possible to update and upgrade unimodal techniques like audio speech processing and motion capture as well as the available hardware that

exists like the VR headsets and even the computer processing and graphical power [JS07]. This led to the possibility of an easier integration of multimodal inputs and outputs to new computer systems and to study a more specific field of study which focuses on this point, as HCI focuses more on unimodal interactions like interfaces.

Multimodal human-computer interaction (MMHCI) studies the interaction of computer systems and humans and justifies the use or improve the usage of multiple modalities as input and output, in order to better the performance of the interaction between computer and user [D02]. The main reason as to why the performance can be increased is that with multimodality it is possible to retrieve and to provide information to the system in new ways which were not possible before the addition of the said modality and removes the need of relying on only the existing ones [For04]. One example of that is the introduction of audio cues that may be used to determine a sound source's identity and location, to estimate the size and certain characteristics of the surrounding physical space, and to identify other characteristics of the environment and simultaneous peripheral activities [Tur14] without the need of having to look to retrieve said information.

This is why that the addition of audio to the already existent VE should not only improve the realism level of the scene but also help the interaction of the user with the current VR system as the user can easier retrieve information without having to move around on the headset to recreate and memorise a 360° view of the scene to know what surrounds him, since you can hear from all of the surrounding space and retrieve information about what exists near you. To validate this point, it will be helpful to do a research and interview users to test the VR app with and without audio to confirm how useful the introduction of a new modality was.

2.3.2 Research Methods

Research in a scientific matter is one practical way of getting data directly from people in order to use it for either the need for valid data for projects or for assembling a conclusion. However, this has to be done carefully and well planned to gather valid and reliable data according to what it is needed to be investigated.

There are two types of research methods that are commonly used, qualitative and quantitative. Quantitative is required when there is a lack of data for a specific problem one wants to solve and it can be quantified and later on be discussed based on the statistics of the results obtained. Qualitative is required when faced by open-ended problems that require subjective data (which can differ depending on the interviewed persons) to formulate hypotheses and expand theories. For the first type two research methods useful for this work's objective are Between Subject/Group Design and Within-Subject Design. For the second one was chosen Grounded Theory.

Between and Within-Subject Design are both types of quantitative research methods which are done when there is the need of comparing multiple similar scenarios where it is needed to compare the impact of the value of a certain variable. In Within-Subject the participants perform all the conditions possible that are needed to test [CGK12]. Therefore this minimises the errors that could be obtained from individual differences, having more solid and coherent results. However, this creates a cross-over effect which might lead to the participant to learn from the previous task,

compromising the data obtained on the next tasks. Between-Subject design avoids this problem since it defends that each individual should perform each task independently [CGK12]. However, this requires a more significant amount of people to interview to have the same statistical power as Within-Subject [BBK14]. This leads to a tough decision of what path to choose between both options to implement a research and already has been an area of interest to study [G G76] [CGK12]. There was already executed a research with to prove some of the objectives this work pursues [PWD13] which was successful using Within-Subject design, exemplifying that there was not any cross-over effect between different scenarios, as the results were valid in the different combinations of tests. However, it will later be decided if this is the approach to follow or if it can be a combination of both.

Grounded Theory is a method of qualitative research which focuses on the analysis of the data assembled, grouping them into similar topics and theorising a solution to the problem [Kha14]. This is useful for subjective matters as it can make conclusions based on the analysis of all submitted reports and conclude based on their similarities. One of the main ways to gather data is by interviews. These can range from structured to open-ended and face-to-face interviews. As for this dissertation, since it already is required the physical presence of the interviewees to participate in the experience it makes sense to do a face-to-face interview regarding their experience. One requirement to be careful before doing the interview is the selection of the participants as they have to be contextualised with the problem. In this case, people with hearing impairment must be completely avoided and also people participating in playing the role of the driver must have some experience in that role. After that, it is necessary to prepare the interview in a humanely way in order to be natural and smoothly evolve by contextualising the problem into asking the desired questions.

2.4 Summary

In this chapter, the literature review done is necessary for the further development of the approaches that are mentioned on the Methodological Approach in the next chapter of this document. It is necessary to correlate the different areas of investigation in order to reach the goal of creating an attention and perception model for the simulation's agents in order to distinguish and evaluate the importance of different audio clips while complementing the VE with an immersive audio soundscape for the city as to improve the interaction of the users with the virtual app and the interaction of the agents within the virtual world and with also the users. Then, it is possible by taking advantage of the mentioned research methods on the HCI section and validate the audio soundscape used, update with necessary changes and also test audio events to analyse and evaluate how impactful it was in order to get data for the attention models and for validity purposes.

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Chapter 3

Methodological Approach

This chapter explains the selection of methods/techniques introduced on the literature review in order to achieve the main goal of this dissertation and try to solve any problems that might come. In order to do so requires the division in three subtasks, namely Audio Processing, Research Study and Audio Classification and Attention Model. This will be explained and introduced individually and independent from the other, but its implementation of the later will have precedence over the past ones as it will functionally require the execution of the former. Briefly, Audio Processing subtopic is responsible for contextualising the environment to sonorize, comparing the real life one to the virtual environment, establishing which sounds are going to be selected and created to do so and its integration process on the current project. Research Study subtopic's goal is to prepare questionnaire questions for the preparation of an experiment to validate the previous Audio Process and also gather human data to use for the following Attention Model. The later subtask will focus around proposing an Attention Model and Classification process that can fit the current project, as well as the implementation process of it.

3.1 Audio Processing

To be able to extract information from the perception to then analyse it after, it is necessary to create a soundscape which fits the current available elements and the overall Unity scene.

First step is to study the most impactful elements on the context of a city environment and then filter the selection of audio events to match the environment to be spatialized and make it as natural as possible comparing the what is experienced on a daily basis. Furthermore, it is also needed to pick specific city events to test what possible reaction people have to them. Overall, the soundscape/atmosphere will follow the specifications and suggestions mentioned in [M B+14], [Reh14] and other information available on the Soundscapes subsection 2.1.2. This will be complemented by the sound classifications set by R. Murray Schafer *et al* [Sch77] to have at least have an experience of each category, as long as it is relevant to a city environment.

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After that it is necessary to create the audio for the selected events. This can be done from scratch or by tweaking and/or trimming samples using a Digital Audio Workstation like Reaper. Then it is necessary to integrate the obtained audio files into Unity. This will be done by using a middleware program called FMOD [Fir19] where it is possible to connect directly to Unity and also allow more manipulation of sound between the two.

3.1.1 Current Context

The current scenario consists of a representation of a city in a VE. To better understand the most relevant elements of the city that characterise its soundscape, it was required to study what people find to listen the most on their daily basis. This was based on the data acquired on [Sou69] that introduced the results on the following figure 2.5 visible at the 2.1.2, along with the study of the city identity urban soundscapes by Rehan *et al* [Reh14]. The following picture 3.1 illustrates the main elements grouped into five specific categories, which will be supplemented by a more in depth description of each points.

Figure 3.1: Audio elements of a city

1. **Traffic Noise.** Nowadays, city soundscapes tend to have its identity changed based on the current technology and human needs. This is more observable on larger cities with the current growth of influx from people and the increase usage in personal vehicles which caused an increase in Noise pollution. Traffic contributes the most for this due to the large amounts of different vehicles that occupy the city streets and by the sounds each emit, being most of considered annoying due to the fact of their intensity, mostly seen in motorcycles, and in some situations even planes. This highly impacts the current soundscape as Rehan found in its study to try and reduce the influence it has over the identity of cities and to

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reduce its impact for improving the life experience on cities for other people. So for this context it is a must to include the overall feeling of traffic movement as it currently is a problem we face.

2. **Spontaneous/Miscellaneous Actions.** This group focuses on a large number of events that happen on a daily basis, which happen based on someones actions. This includes cellphones ring, music playing like either from someones loudspeakers or from propaganda/working stations or vehicles, objects falling or being moved, metal clanks, whistles, bells and so long. Most soundmarks can be integrated on this group due to their uniqueness. The actions that lead to this usually are random or are hard to predict when they happen despite knowing the original source.
3. **People.** This is also a obvious choice has one of the core elements of a city are its citizens. The sound events originated by humans include body movements like walking and their voice. This introduces a problem has the volume of the noise people make is not always proportional to the amount of people. This is influenced by the social status of the current location and time. On the sidewalks it is common to hear a mumbling sound of people talking but it is more easily identifiable the presence of voices near schools, popular kids parks or on certain events like football stadiums during games. Otherwise, it is also possible to hear almost no sound on more calm places like larger parks or near suburban areas. To summarise, human activity depends on the social interaction, time and places the city provides.
4. **Sirens and Horns/Rings.** Although this is included on traffic noise group, there was the need to separate due to its uniqueness. Sirens and Honks distinguish themselves from other sounds due to their repetitive pattern. Unlike the car engines and other mechanical sounds, these are louder to inform people of their presence and/or involve indirectly an action. Some of those patterns are common among similar cultures but might differ so slightly to still make simple its recognition.
5. **Nature.** Even on larger cities with not much interaction with the natural environment, there is always present something that represents it. This can be either animal sounds, weather related events or the type of geolocation the city is inserted. More cities are prone to have more wind depending on where they are build and some have exclusive atmosphere due to this like having a beach nearby that makes possible to hear the sea waves, something not possible in other case scenarios. This also leads to the current biodiversity available which limits the current soundscape experience. Using the previous example, seagulls are common among in cities with rivers or sea next to them.

With this information it is possible to start narrowing down some key components a city must have. However, some components have ambiguities on them due to the conditions presented on certain elements of the city, specially the Nature one. To further filter the necessary audio events, it is necessary to evaluate the current scenario.

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The VE city was created on Unity and has some diversity of distinct elements and sections. To start, first it is necessary to check the surrounding environments of the city to classify where it locates.

Figure 3.2: Geolocation of the Unity City

As it is possible to visualise on the figure 3.2, the city is located right next to a small beach and surrounded by the sea, so having a similar to other city soundscapes with the same elements can be a good representation for this one. Nature wise, not much else is visible, no trees, no mountains or increase in land relief with the exception of the distant one visible and also no animals are visible. However, it is still possible to introduce to certain audio events that indicate such presence without reducing the realism level. Some quality of life additions to this are also the change/update of elements listenable according to the distance of the source. So, the sound of waves of seagulls would be more intense the closer it is to the beach or the sea.

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Figure 3.3: Example of city road

Visually, the city contains what to be expected of such place: cars, buildings, roads and people, generically speaking. A clear factor that gives an identity to this city is the uncommon large number of parked cars throughout the whole city. Every road on the city, with the exception of highways, has a parking place and most of them are completely occupied with cars. The introduction of some spontaneous events like car alarms or radio music on this would not be that misplaced since the abnormally activity this city appears to have. The city buildings also have some variety of type and architecture but most of them appear to be residence types of building, not having a clear identity of them. The only exception is a football (soccer) field but can only be identified as such by an overhead view since it is blocked by white walls. However, the definition of what a social building should look like is perceived differently on every culture, so again, having a more populated location would not interfere with the overall soundscape. The permanent silence or stationary audio levels throughout the city should evolve depending on the place to not give the feeling of being at the same location. This would be fine on smaller or less populated villages, which is not the case of this city. So, some variants of sound are mandatory to better upgrade the soundscape.

Besides the parking cars, there are only two types/brand of other vehicles that move on and populate the city's roads. These are the car cockpit and the Archisim vehicles.

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Figure 3.4: Moveable cars. Left is the Archisim vehicle, right is the cockpit

Archisim [EA07] is a backend controller responsible for the behaviour of the vehicle illustrated above. This manipulates the current speed based on the visual perceptions and positions of other elements present on the scene. This prototypes a self driven car which moves between previously defined points on a server running at the same time as the scene. This requires a connection between unity and the server to exchange information to update its current status. The cockpit is a user driven car that people can use to move freely through the city. This functions close to how a semi-automatic car does and can be controlled by either the computer keyboard or using a racing wheel setup. This limits the current diversity of the streets as there are only two types of different engines to be distinguished on the traffic, and one of them is permanently listened if the user is driving the cockpit.

Figure 3.5: City pedestrians

The last group of elements available on the current environment are the pedestrians. Likewise to the Archisim vehicles, these are controlled by a backend service that also bases its behaviour on the receive information regarding the visual perceptions of the environment. The difference between both of these groups is that both servers are independent and different from another and

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the path set up is defined on the unity environment for the pedestrians, as opposed to the Archisim vehicles. On the scene, it is created a graph of map positions which the user can walk. Then, between these graphs, it is selected a set of source points and points of interests to the pedestrians walk. Both of these are selected randomly for each new pedestrians spawned to improve the population movement of the city. As they do not verbally communicate with each other, the only available sounds it should emit are body movements like walking. There must be a part where some talking/mumbling should appear but it will have a different audio source rather than strictly having on specific pedestrians. Some interaction can also be done between the cockpit and the pedestrians to introduce some vocal effects to them. This can be a simple collision effect or some passing way to much close to it.

3.1.2 Audio Event Selection

Considering the context introduced, either the generic city elements or the available ones on unity, it is now possible to proceed to the selection of the audio events to create with the purpose to sonorize the VE. Note that the non existing elements or limitation of those on unity do not deprive its further implementation and can be later on added to help improve the city realism.

The selection of audio events lead to a division of four distinct event groups, ambience, pedestrian, car and miscellaneous. The reason for this is due to the small amount of elements existent on the current scene which can be listed as: pedestrians, Archisim cars, car cockpit, parked vehicles, human-made structures and nature. Each of this groups has distinct audio events that do not correlate with the other either on a context level or category type and have different purpose within the city context.

Ambience Events	
AE1	Highway ambience
AE2	Quieter city ambience
AE3	Busy park ambience

Table 3.1: Ambience related audio events

The ambience is a background sound which mixes all surrounding elements into one focal point. In other words, it is the atmosphere characteristic of a certain place due to all elements that exist there (human and non human). These can be categorised as Keynote sounds (by being background continuous sounds), sounds and society, as well as natural sounds. How accurate the recording of one ambience is can change depending on the person listening to due to the experience each one of them has or by some regional aspects. Having barking on some city park can be unrealistic to some people or even hearing distant airplanes. However some generalisation points can be done to achieve a good synthesised ambience.

The selected ambiances available at the table 3.1 correspond to common large city sections. Highway ambience relate to the outskirts of the city near highways were it is common to hear cars

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passing by. Quieter city ambience has less white noise and wind effects relatively to the highway one, as well as less car noise. The busy park is a mix of children playing and people mumbling, which can be mistaken by a school. This will be present near a specific part of the Unity scene despite not having specific defined buildings. There can be also heard seagulls on the first two audio events to introduce a more noticeable nature touch on them.

These three events should be sufficient to sonorize a large city as to give some diversity and not have a stall background noise whilst driving by the city, which can indicate the current place or status the person is, just like in a real life situation.

Pedestrian Events	
PE1	Collision
PE2	Walking

Table 3.2: Pedestrian related audio events

Car Events	
CE1	Engine 1
CE2	Engine 2
CE3	Turning on
CE4	Honk 1
CE5	Honk 2
CE6	Brake
CE7	Crash

Table 3.3: Car related audio events

Pedestrian and Car events are by definition signal sounds, as it is necessary for an action to occur in order to the event be played, as opposed to the keynote ones which are constant. The selection of events visible in 3.2 and 3.3 try to cover all available actions that can be done by both pedestrians and cars. It was distinguished two versions for both engine and honks due to the fact that there are only two types of cars that move, the Archisim and the cockpit cars. To not mistake any of them, it was important to distinguish these events as they are prevalent on a traffic daily basis.

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Other Events	
OE1	Police Sirens
OE2	Firefighter Sirens
OE3	Ambulance Sirens
OE4	Anti-theft Alarm
OE5	Ice cream Truck music

Table 3.4: Miscellaneous audio events

Lastly there are miscellaneous events. The siren and music events can be classified as either signal sounds or event soundmarks depending on how frequent and where they happen. Contrasting with the previous events, the alarm acts as a keynote sound. Despite most of them not being available on the scene, these are common elements of a city soundscape and including them is important to give the city some identity.

Furthermore, the selection of these sounds 3.4 was also targeted to test the attention of the user towards very specific actions that happen on a city. The Ice cream truck specifically as it can be considered out of context to some people not familiarised with the music or just find strange for it to be there. The alarm as sirens are spontaneous events associated to a specific vehicle and will be used to test the behaviour people have by listening to the audio clip when near by. It will be interesting to see how the people categorise the different events as there is ambiguity on the definitions and also the levels of importance one gives to them on a given context of time and space.

3.1.3 Audio Creation, Tweaking and Integration

The digital audio workstation used was Reaper [Rea19], which contains a large number of features and plugins to create, mix and change current audio files. Most of the audio files were sampled by pre-existing ones provided by the BBC bank [BBC19] and then tweaking for noise or *clicking* removal. However, there was the need to create from scratch certain audio clips like the human steps, white static background noise heard on the ambience, wind and distance car effects.

These were then imported onto FMOD [Fir19] to finalise the audio event creation. This software has also audio manipulation capabilities which will be proved useful next. Some events are multi tracked, meaning they contain several audio clips that can be played at the same time. Most relevant ones are the ambience events due to the different elements available on them (seagulls, cars, nature sounds for example). An example of this can be seen below.

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Figure 3.6: FMOD Interface snippet

This makes possible to do any changes to any of the tracks and get the final result that will be obtained on the scene. This is also useful to attribute variables that can update certain aspect of a certain track or the whole event like the volume, so at specific parts of the city a track can change its volume by updating the variable value. By looking that the previous picture 3.6, the increase of the parameter Volume Birds increases the volume of the corresponding track. Variables can also create loops on specific time sections by continuously replaying a pre-established audio section. This is done, for example, on the ambulance sirens to continuously play the sound when a condition is met. On the example shown it is set to have a continuous loop stated by the blue bar right below the timeline. This is useful for ambience events because they always play during the scene. The needs to have extra work in order to create proper loop regions without noticing any difference between the loop ending and starting point.

To integrate FMOD onto Unity requires the installation of the FMOD unity package on the current project and the selection of the audio banks produced. The audio banks are exported by FMOD which hold information of all audio events, meaning audio files, parameters, assigned plugins like the distance attenuation which is responsible to calculate the volume depending on how far the source is. After that is recognised by the project, it is then possible to assign to different objects to audio events or program when certain event should happen. After this, it is possible to connect both softwares and update in real time any audio event whilst running the scene. The change of variable values automatically update the assigned effect on the audio events without the need for both so. FMOD provides a script that checks for collision between tags of objects to update variable values of certain events. This makes possible to make dynamic ambiances by selecting different zones and updating parameter values of each event.

However, the current setup requires changes to adapt the system to be compatible to binaural audio, which was mentioned in 2.1.3. To do this, it was chosen to use the Google Resonance Audio plugin [Goo19]. Resonance features a high fidelity spatial audio experience by simulating how sound waves interact with human ears and the environment. This focuses on some problems

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brought by the human anatomy in 2.1.1 like the Interaural time differences or interaural level differences which is implemented by using HRTFs referenced in 2.1.3 to simulate real sound wave interaction with human ears. The decoding can easily adapt to any current format available so by default no special update is necessary and it is immediately binaural ready, So, the necessary changes are configuration the audio output to use the Resonance plugin on Unity and updating the FMOD project. In order to use the plugin it is necessary to change the Master Bus mixer of the project to use Resonance Audio Listener or pass all events to a new mixer that uses the said listener. Second and last step is to update all audio events to use Resonance Audio Source instead of the FMOD Spatializer.

Figure 3.7: Resonance Audio Source plugin interface

This is responsible for updating the output of the track to use the Resonance parameter functions such as the gain volume and distance range or other events visible above. 2D events like the Ambience events which do not use the spatializer also need to add this despite not using distance attenuation. The difference being that the Distance Attenuation setting will be set to constant and that the spread knob value must be set to 360 degrees to give a surround feeling. This can be seen on the previous figure 3.7. After all is set and compiled, the Unity scene is now 3D Audio ready and the development phase can move almost exclusively to Unity to setup the events.

3.2 Research Study

To validate if the proposed method of audio selection and sonorization process was well executed and to collect data necessary to use on the attention model, there must have a preparation phase to check what is needed to test, collect, change and how to do all of the above.

To check if the previous method was valid the research must contain a questionnaire to ask people for feedback regarding the experience they had. This is to be an approach to evaluate on a scale the realism of the experience. To do so, the user has to have a term of comparison to evaluate how realistic the soundscape is has by having one run on the environment won't be enough to a user to say if it is realistic or not. This would also have problems in case the behaviour inside the VR world is something that is not expected, like having pedestrians flying. One work around that is to have two runs, one with and the other without audio. This will make possible for direct comparisons between the two situations to check either the realism levels but also the impact

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the audio scene has over the audioless. This also provides valid results in case of any unexpected action to happen that could reduce the realism levels by simply asking how superior the experience was, in terms of realism, on the audio scenario, instead of asking how the realism was during the whole experience.

This is achievable by implementing a research using Within Subject group and Grounded theory, similar to the one done by Poeschl *et al* [PWD13]. Both of these are HCI research methods that were explained on the 2.3. The reason why it was picked Within Subject over Between Group subject is not only by the need to have a reference point to have comparison points on different scenarios, but also due to the lack of time and resources to have a large number of people to participate on the experiment. As seen in [BBK14] it is worse to do a Between subject research method with a lower amount of people compared has produces worst quality of results on average.

However, Within subject design introduces some flaws that have to be looked that. Since this creates a cross-over effect from the previous task, some aspects cannot be tested on the second one. As such, having triggerable events that are the same to both case scenarios would lead to the user already acknowledging on what was going to happen. For example, having a ambulance suddenly appearing on a intersection every time would produce invalid data on the second run due to the user already expecting it. This at first seems a big problem if there was the need to force the user to look at something when it produces audio and to expect it to not look when there is not any audio but, on the contrary, it is what it needs to be study. If the user always looks at a object, despite of it not having any sound, adding it on the first place would be useless to improve the attention. However, when running the second phase without audio, the user already knows the position of things and removes the element of surprise. The attempt to fix this is to add events which are randomly triggered so it changes every time, making it still unpredictable and still maintaining new elements to test on. This can also be fixed by creating different ways to reach the same goal like, for example, having different routes on both experiments. Both elements will be taken in count when preparing the experiment on the forth chapter of this document. However some cross-over effects might still happen due to the change of behaviour some users may have due to the abstention of audio. For instance, driving with or without audio might change depending on each person. It can also cause people to have more difficulties driving on the first run as the user gets adapted to the current system comparing to the second one, so testing the driving skills might be compromised for both cases.

Next comes the establishment of specific questionnaire questions (QQs) to guide through the whole setup of the Unity Scene. The main, generically speaking, points chosen to be focused on are the acknowledgement of a played audio event and its identification of presence and location and the reaction the user has. In other words, the points of interest are to test if the people on the city pay attention to a sound to know if it exists, where it comes from and if they look at it or do a jump scare, for example. The reason for this is because most people have different attention levels whilst driving on a city space. Some can only recognise certain elements exist through sound while others are ignorant of such during their daily routine. There is no interest in studying how a person reacts to certain audio events if it did not even notice it existed. After that, it is also

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necessary to have questionnaire questions to evaluate the impact on the overall experience with and without audio , as mentioned on the previously. So far, the current questionnaire questions can be resumed on the table 3.5.

QQ 1	Did you feel that you were in a City environment ?
QQ 2	Did you felt that you experienced real life situations?
QQ 3	Did you manage to identify more elements on the audio city ? If so which ones were.
QQ 4	Was there any element exclusively identifiable by sound ? If so which ones.
QQ 5	Was there any element you found out of context ?
QQ 6	Did you identify any ambiances or elements of it during the experiment?
QQ 7	Overall, Did audio impact your experience with the Virtual Environment ?
QQ 8	Did you notice any changes on your behaviour on the sonORIZED version ?

Table 3.5: Starting Questionnaire Questions

The QQs number 1, 2, 7 and 8 represent the need to evaluate the environment to check if the realism levels were increased on the audio experience as already discussed. The QQs 5 and 6 are useful to determine how different people perceive ambience and if they pay attention to not only that but if they acknowledge uncommon or misplaced sounds like the Ice cream truck that was discussed on the Audio Selection phase. The missing questionnaire questions are targeted to test the attention levels of the participants to see how many sounds they identify during the experience and if they were only able to identify due to their audio clip. These eight questions plus additional comments given by the participants are enough to determine the impact of audio on the users experience on the current scenario and also test some basic attention parameters.

To better analyse the impact audio has on determined events, it was needed to add more questionnaire questions targeted to specific objects to test the interaction. These are available in 3.6.

QQ 9	Did you need to look at a specific point to find out the source of X?
QQ 10	Did you find out which element produced X ? If so characterise it
QQ 11	How many elements produced X ? Did you notice any difference between the sound?
QQ 12	Did you hear X ? If so, when was it easier to detect

Table 3.6: Second round of questionnaire questions

With this QQs it is possible to get a better understanding on how people perceive and react to certain events. Starting with a generic free question where the user can list all elements he/she desires, the other questions restrict to specific events which produced a X audio clip. This will test if they know the object to properly identify it instead of associating a sound with an event. This checks if people will look at a car honking, for example, and determine which car model or colour played instead of just answering car or vehicle, which would be a generic straight answer that would not require any information obtained. This will also test if people distinguish between variations of sound for a same group of objects or if they ignore due to the similarities they have.

Lastly it is also interesting to see if changes to a occurring audio event are noticed during the execution of the test.

This will be the base for executing the VR immersive experience with a variety of people and for doing the questionnaire after the experiment. This will also guide the suggestion section of each participant to get more constructive feedback. The specification of events to test and the implementation of said questionnaire will be on the following chapter.

3.3 Audio Classification and Attention Model

For this topic will be an approach to the creation of an audio attention model and classification process and how to connect them to the already existing project. Both of these models are necessary for the proper identification of elements present on the current audio spectrum and the attention model to receive this information and provide feedback on how the user should behave. The following figure 3.8 is a proposed architecture for the whole process described before.

Figure 3.8: Proposed architecture for the project

There are two distinct systems on this architecture, the Unity and Python Server. Unity contains the scenario representing the city. This is an agglomerate of different unity scenes, each containing a specific responsibility. One of the scenes contains the graphical part of the city, other the collisions of the buildings and stationary objects, one responsible for setting up the Archisim vehicles controller, other responsible for setting up the pedestrians controller and the last one is either the pedestrian or the car cockpit. The target for this dissertation will focus only on the driver cockpit only. All of this achieves the final result of a virtual interactive environment where all agents can interact with it and themselves, as well as with the users actions.

The components mentioned on the figure 3.8 of the Unity system are context and perceptions. Context represents the current state, at the time of execution, of the scenario, which can be either the position or other state of a specific agent. The perception of an agent represents what the object understands of the environment. This is an approach to represent the human sensory system

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by perceiving the surrounding elements using, for example what the object can *observe*. For the proposed architecture, this would represent the current perceived sound, resulting into a complex audio signal wave composed of different audio signals from different sources at distinct locations. With this, it would be possible to have almost all information of the elements available at a certain location of the agent, as long as they have some audio event linked to them or one of their actions, so it could make them identifiable by evaluating the obtained signal wave and not by checking the other objects internal status, attempting to be more realistic and avoiding relying on checking for external objects information.

For the correct perception of the environment, this would require to have a system which mixes all audio signals audible at a certain location and that can solve some of the restrict certain audio features to match the limitations of the hearing system, like the distance possible to hear a certain sound, distinguish the source location orientation. As already referenced in 2.1.3 and 3.1.3, using FMOD and Resonance Audio already implements everything mentioned and provides a good user realism level of experience. The challenge is to obtain not the user output but any agent output to get the resulting audio signal at that location. This will depend on the current Unity software limitations as well as the documentation available to the public.

This intel would then be transferred to the second system, the Python Server. Just like the pedestrian and Archisim components, this would be responsible for all logic evolving the behaviour the agent and also to identify what they have perceived. This would require to run concurrently to the other existing servers and to have its own unique channel of communication. This is achievable by using HTTP requests and establishing an internal protocol to differentiate the type of information sent and received. The two components python server would have internally are the Classification system and the Attention Model.

The Audio Classification will require using a CNN, as mentioned in subsection 2.2.1 and a audio dataset in order to train and provide good results for matching process of the input audio signal/file. The selected CNN to use is the one proposed by Qiuqiang Kong *et al* [Yu+18] which has embedded an attention model on it, as seen in 2.2.2. The CNN was built using Tensorflow platform, a open-source platform that provides a set of tools and frameworks that make possible the creation and training of machine learning methods. Along side Tensorflow it uses Keras, a high level neural network API. This provides a simpler and faster ways of creating and prototyping neural networks such as CNNs by making more intuitive to replicate models and provides GPU support, increasing the processing power.

For the selected CNN model, it provides four distinct model type configurations that change the NN decision level and consequently the overall accuracy of the classification. These are average pooling decision level, max pooling decision level and then the already studied single and multi level attention models. The average and max pooling efficiency depends based on the audio signal form as max polling will base on more extreme values while pooling whereas the average extracts features more smoothly and has a better performance overall. The architecture models for single and multi attention are visible on the figure 2.7.. Both of these four models will be tested to check the impact of having an attention model associated with the CNN and to check what the

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best option is for this context. This will be done once the whole system is fully operational.

The audio dataset chosen to train the CNN is the Google's audio dataset [Aud19b]. This uses data of over 2 million different audio signals extracted from YouTube videos. Exploring the ontology, it is possible to analyse all available categories of audio extracted and possible to label while training and running the neural network. One limitation this has is how unbalanced the dataset is. The clear focus on this dataset seems to be on the music section since half of the annotations available on the videos are related to music. This can create bias towards the final results on this context as it can provide less precision in terms of classification for other sounds, since the resulting NN will be more targeted in classifying music related terms. In fact, vehicle and car labels only appear on about eight percent of the total available videos, which can be problematic for the accuracy for this context. For the default audio file used to test this CNN, which is a metallic audio effect, the results obtained are precise but the confidence levels can be ambiguous due to having more than five different labels with more than sixty percent confidence, half of them music related (instruments for example) and the other ones associated with vehicle or siren events, and then the bell sound, which is the most close comparison to real life terms. This data was obtained used a balanced dataset, which can be selected to do on the code for this CNN, to remove the excess of certain label events to improve the performance. Even for a car horn effect, despite having high precision values for the elements, which were vehicle, bell and car horn (which is a member of the bell event group) it would still require some analysis for the result because the most accurate label obtained is for vehicle. Despite being technically correct, it is not the most precision answer and for what is needed, it would be incorrect. Furthermore, this is only by analysing single audio signals, so it will be necessary to address this problem later on after the integration of this NN within the system.

Another limitation of using this CNN is the high processing power it requires to train. It took approximately five hours to fully train it in order to obtain the example results it should return. This also required some bug fixing on the provided code as it contained errors on some of those functionalities. One of them is the need of having every iteration of training saved on a temporary file, for the future iterations to update on that data. However, each iteration occupies 34 mega bytes and it was constantly saving them despite not having the need for them, because it only requires the previous iteration to update the values that would cause a massive disk mitigation as it requires a high number of iterations to achieve the desired results. It also contained flaws analysing the audio files as it was very limited to certain audio types and configuration. After some bug fixing, the NN was fully operational but it still takes some processing graphical power to run the classification for a single audio file. For a ten second audio clip it would take close to thirty seconds to give results. This is problematic to execute once both systems run at the same time due to hardware constrains and can compromise the reaction time to obtain the response to be later on used by the agents.

After obtaining the results, this would then send the information of the perceived elements and send it to the Attention Model component. The proposed model would be a probabilistic model using the data obtained on the Research Study subsection 3.2 and then control the behaviour the agent should have based on the perception results. Such behaviour would evolve the correct or

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partial identification of the audio source or just the acknowledgement of said audio event, the position/orientation of the object relative to the agent and lastly if and when required to move to the source to identify the object or just to replicate a reaction movement. This would demand storing information relative to all audio events and the behaviours mentioned previously, then applying said probabilistic data obtained from the user and then return to the Unity system via the HTTP communication channel to instruct the agent of said information. The context would provide information about the position of nearby objects to then, if the case, correlate the object with the audio event and complement the information to be sent. All of this would then be a approach to simulate the audio cognitive system by distinguishing a listenable part (Unity) and sending back to be processed and proceeding to get the corresponding behaviour(Python Server), replicating a basic concept of the human auditory system.

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Chapter 4

Experiment, Results and Discussion

The chapter Experiment, Results and Discussion describes the implementation of all audio events into the VE and make the necessary arrangements for executing the Research Study experiment. It contains an in-depth explanation of said testing variables, explains the research protocol created and then presents the obtained results from all participants.

Finally, the data received is analysed to decide whether or not the chosen implementation method for the sonorization process was the most adequate and to test the impact audio add on the perception of the elements, meaning if it helped not only the user experience overall but also if the user can gain more information regarding its surroundings and if it triggers any reaction to any of the audio events.

After said analysis, some data limitations constrained the proper purpose they would have had on the attention model creation. Also, some software restrictions limited the information extraction from the auditory perceptions that led to changing the proposed architecture system mentioned before at the figure [3.8](#).

4.1 Scenario Preparations

In order to create the scenario for the testing, it is important to check and create the elements that do not yet exist on the scene and are needed to complement the selected audio events to implement. The mentioned existing audio files selected to test the interaction mentioned in subsection [3.1.2](#) range from ambient to pedestrian and vehicle sounds and were created previously using Reaper and then created into complex audio events using FMOD, using the techniques mentioned at the subsection [3.1.3](#). To follow this up, it is necessary to select appropriate hardware to use for the experiment.

The different ambient events represent the background sound the tester is constantly listening. Said events are a major part of the current soundscape experience. In order for this to be realistic and function as intended, this will be attached to the main camera of the scene and will always

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act as a surround sound due to the camera being the representation of the user's head and always having an audio listener attached to it. All other audio events are object attached and have a maximum audible range where the audio volume/intensity evolves to zero at maximum range. There are three current available ambient sounds which will have to intertwine and update according to the current location to give a sensation of movement between different locations.

Some restrictions will lead to a reduced spectrum of available audio events regarding the traffic experience. Both types of cars, cockpit and Archisim, were expected to have the same audio events being both objects cars. However, due to behaviour limitations of the Archisim vehicles such as having no colliders, not being able to distinct some visual perceptions like the proximity to the cockpit and the fact that it is extremely conservative while driving, the following events will not be noticed while running the experiment: honk, brake and crash. Nonetheless, this only reduces some annoyance experience of the traffic expected but this will be compensated on other events.

To trigger the car alarm event, one specific of the many parked cars were selected to have a random opportunity to play the said event. The selected car was the yellow Volkswagen car as there are already a significant number of these present on the scene. The event will trigger once the user passes close by the selected car and will have a thirty-three percent chance of successfully play the audio event. The reason for this is to not cluster the soundscape and damage the overall experience the people experimenting on the scenario have, whilst maintaining a relatively good number of triggered alarm events. This, however, still creates an effect of annoyance on the driver as expected. This was already mentioned on [MB+14] and [Reh14] on the Soundscapes subsection 2.1.2 where it is important to keep balance of the noise pollution based on the iconic aspect of the city. On this particular city represented by the scenario, there exists a large quantity of parked cars which leads to the idea that it represents a busy city, bringing a significant amount of alarm and engine sounds overall that it is going to be recreated with this event. The same thought process was used for the following paragraph regarding the ambulance event. Both of these types of events shall compensate for the lack of honk events available on the soundscape to maintain the expected noise pollute ambience.

The missing audio events which do not have a current correspondent 3D model available on the scene are the two ambulances plus the ice cream audio events. For this, based on the already existing van prefabs, it was adapted to have two different ambulance textures and one for the ice cream truck. The later one does not have a direct co-relation of image and sound to add an unexpected factor to the experience which is one of the factors to study, as previously discussed. The following figure 4.1 contain three images, each represents a new prefab to be sonorized with the respective events.

Figure 4.1: Created prefabs for the scenario. First two images represent the ambulances and the second one the ice cream truck

Just like the yellow Volkswagen car, both of the ambulance events are also triggered by passing nearby the object, but have a larger range (both of listenable range and trigger zone) and are not random. The ice cream truck is unique, meaning there will be only one of its kind during the experience and will be located on an accessible view zone. This has a small yellow symbol who represents a known political party. Its trigger zone is located further away from the object, so it plays outside the field of view when driving by the cockpit car. The reason for this is to see if the user can identify the presence of the car and how well they identify it (by either the political party or by the audio) as well as when they perceive the identity of the object. During the experience, it will either expected for the participants to make any comment during this part either by finding the presence of the sound weird or by the unexpected presence of the type of van. It will also be asked if they can recognise the audio after passing the zone and if they knew the source of it.

Furthermore, there is also required to prepare the necessary hardware for the experiment. Since this is a VR experiment it is a must to have a VR Headset. The VR Headset selected was the oculus HTC Vive which provides a fully immersive experience by giving a 360-degree controller and headset tracking. This uses SteamVR Tracking and which makes it possible to run this scenario in VR.

Figure 4.2: Oculus HTC Vive

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This headset is very comfortable as it is possible to readjust its size to fit most people's heads and also has a large frontal view to enable the usage of glasses to avoid any vision problems the participants might have. This uses base stations to cover the headset movement and need to have a clear view of it, so no interference shall happen between them and the HTC Vive.

To drive the car, the participants will use the Logitech's G27 Racing wheel. This setup provides a steering wheel to control the car's direction with two back triggers that control the current gear, increasing the gear with the right and decreasing with the left. Additionally, this setup includes a set of pedals similar to most cars. Unlike what most people are used to, there is no need to use the clutch pedal for switching gears.

Figure 4.3: Logitech G27 steering wheel and pedals

Lastly, to reproduce the city's audio to further increase the immersive experience requires the usage of headphones. The Behringer HPS 3000 Studio-Headphone provides a good audio quality fidelity and has a good frequency balance overall and should fit most people.

Figure 4.4: Behringer HPS3000

Next step is to properly set up the scenario with the created objects and populate the current environment with it. Then, it is necessary to define the different ambient zones available as well as setting up a path to follow and adjust the necessary objects to make them test ready and to be interactable with the participants.

4.2 Test Setup

The scenario was previously created based on the Archisim Vehicle simulator structure to match all the streets pre-defined. This includes not only roads, but buildings to make the scene more realistic, as well as parked cars on the designated places. On the following picture, it is possible to see a top view of the zone selected for the people to be able to freely drive.

Figure 4.5: Top view of the Unity Scene

This zone is limited by walls which contain an arrow to point the direction the user should go in order to avoid visiting undesired locations of the scene. The AI controlled pedestrian and Archisim vehicles, as seen at subchapter 3.1.1, require restarting at every start of the experiment to initialise the repositioning process. This process will also be limited to make these agents move through this zone only, as it would not make much sense otherwise. The location randomisation of pedestrians has a large enough quantity of source and destination points to select from to provide a correct flow of movement of the city's citizens by giving the possibility to have free walking people around most places.

However, the free will of choice of movement by the testers is not only limited by the walls surrounding this zone but also the existence of certain mandatory points each participant must pass by in order to finish the test.

Figure 4.6: Mandatory places of the Scene

The yellow circle is the starting point of the car cockpit, the red circle is the ending point of the test and the blue ones are points of interest. All of these last points must be visited with no specific order. Despite not having a clearly defined path, a shorter path will be chosen to avoid taking too much time travelling through all available locations. The blue zones have fixed elements or scripted actions necessary to test the interaction with the participants. These range from either interaction with ambulances, the ice cream van or the local ambient sound. On the next figures 4.7, 4.8 and 4.9 it will be possible to identify which zones contain the said elements.

Figure 4.7: Position of all yellow cars

The red rectangles marked on the 4.7 figure represent all yellow cars that exist on the current scene. As mentioned before in section 4.1 the odds for it to play are thirty-three percent, adding to the fact there are of more than thirty yellow cars throughout the scenario, plus the user should pass

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by most cars in order to reach every mandatory point, which makes it almost guaranteed that the alarm sound effect should play at least twice with avoiding over saturation of said sound effect. This important as to not compromise realism and immersive levels of the test.

Figure 4.8: Position of all yellow ambulances

Figure 4.9: Position of all white ambulances

The previous two pictures 4.8 and 4.9 represent the position of all yellow and white ambulances respectively. Comparing to the 4.6 figure we can safely say that the tester will pass by, at least once by each type of ambulance. One of the blue circles contains both ambulance variations to make it easier to check for the difference in sounds and to directly compare both of them. The number of overall ambulances is significantly reduced compared to the number of yellow cars to avoid overloading the audio experience with ambulances by constantly playing the sirens as it always turns on depending on the current user location.

Figure 4.10: Ambience zone locations

Lastly, the figure 4.10 represents each division of the ambience soundscape. Every single one of them has a characteristic which makes it distinguishable from the others. According to what we wanted to study as shown in 3.1.2 it is important to define a clear zone where these belong as well as avoiding constantly repeating the same soundscape to not deteriorate the location identification process. In order to fulfil these requirements, two major zones were created, the red and the yellow areas and two secondary zones, the blue and green.

The red zone is a windy ambient with background cars passing by, similar to the highways or suburban areas near highways or busy roads, to correspond to the visual aspect. The blue area is much quieter than the red one since the white background noise is less intense in decibel levels, which increase as you approximate to the highway at the left side of the picture, and includes an increasing seagull sound as you approach the beach. The location from the right start point to the left ending point will unconsciously transition both of these soundscapes and provide a natural change to what happens in real life, as well as an opportunity to see if the user can check the evolution of the background sound.

The secondary zones are easier distinct from the previous ones due to a more abrupt change on the current soundscape. The blue area introduces to a more crowded noisy ambient, mainly composed of children, to give the impression of being near a school or a more family environment. Contrasting to the other ambient areas, the green zone does not change the current background sound but adds a new audio source to the existing environment. The event added is the ice cream audio event and will be a focused object event as opposed to the ambience events, which reproduced directly on the camera audio output. As explained on the Scenario Preparations section 4.1, this will trigger after passing by the van but will remain listenable at the range shown on the figure 4.10. This will try to persuade people into forcing to look into the van or simply just notice any change of the driver's behaviour or perception. All ambience events overlap with the mandatory places scattered on the map to ensure every ambience is experienced.

4.3 Experiment Protocol

To collect usable data from participants for the creation of the audio attention model, it is important to establish a set of rules in order to not compromise any data into invalid usage. As so, it is necessary to create an experimental protocol for the respective VR experiment to collect data within the same controlled environment, so every user can have the same experience others would have had.

To guarantee this, it is necessary for all the equipment to work as intended, as well as everything on the Unity Project. One particular test required two random subjects to evaluate the environment beforehand. This is important to test if the Resonance plugin is working and if they can distinguish between all available directions, either both sides, frontal or back. For this, it was created an environment with four audio sources to test if both users could distinguish different orientations. Both of them were correct every time, which green-lighted the continuation of the procedure.

Then, it is necessary to outline what the participant should and should not do during the immersive experience, as well as informing of all the content they strictly need to know without spoiling any vital information. All of this is necessary to gather results for the established QQs, as well as data for the audio attention model. The following is the experimental protocol defined to ensure a systematic approach for every experiment:

- **Explain the Experiment:** Give a brief explanation of what the participant is going to test. This involves the objectives of the dissertation and to get a general idea of what his/her contribution is to this work.
- **Demonstrate the usage of the material:** Explain how all equipment works and their limited functionalities, like the restricted movement of the gaming Wheel, the usage of the back wheel triggers and pedals and also warn the user for the dangers caused by being in an immersive VR world (dizziness or motion sickness for example).
- **State the conditions of the experiment:** Remind the users of the experiment world's limitations (presence of slow-moving cars on the road and unnatural pedestrian activity) and how to react to this. The participant should also follow the orders issued they will receive during all phases of the experiment and the directions present on the scene.
- **Ask the participant for consent:** After explaining all previous points, if the participant agrees to be part of the experiment, the declaration of consent form is given to the participant which it should be read and signed in case of acceptance. This document is available on the Appendix [A.1](#).
- **Randomise the order:** One flip coin is thrown at the beginning of each experiment. The result delineates the order of which the audio phase will take place. Heads the user first runs with headphones and consequently with audio and tails the opposite.

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- **Initialisation:** Every experiment and its current phase must have the same conditions as the previous or the future ones so it is mandatory that the Archisim system and Pedestrian servers are restarted before the execution of the scene. It is also important to rename the log file between phases to distinguish between audio and audioless runs.
- **Start the run:** Depending on the current order of the phase, the researcher shall remove or put the headphones to the user. Then, at the beginning of each phase, it is checked if the participant can currently see, hear and manipulate the gaming setup and fix any anomaly. After that, the user can start driving the car and follow the directions given until it reaches the final destination. In case of sickness or any discomfort felt by the test, the user can stop and rest until ready for restarting the run or, in the worst case scenario, give up. Once finished, the researcher ensures the log file is updated by pressing the 'J' key which saves any unrecorded event. Then, the user can remove the VR headset and rest for some time, until preparations are done for the second run. Once ready, this step is repeated one more time and then the practical test is completed.
- **Fill the questionnaire:** When the 2 phases of the experiment are finished and all equipment is removed, the participant is presented with a questionnaire to fill.
- **Thank for the participation:** After successfully completing every task, the researcher thanks the participant for cooperating.

Whilst the participant is playing on the scene, the directions given by the researcher have the purpose to shorten the time between the mandatory points of interest as seen in 4.6. The user must always try to behave according to the same legal driving rules, to enforce a more realistic driving experience. The exceptions to this are for some behaviour limitations regarding the Archisim vehicles and the pedestrians. Pedestrians do not often show interest in crossing to different street margins despite just standing near crosswalks at some points. They also might stop at the middle of the road for an undefined period of time. When this happens, the participants can move around the pedestrians without having to wait for their reaction. The Archisim Vehicles have a very conservative acceleration and speed and also can stop indefinitely near crosswalks. Since they do not have any physical collisions enabled, the users can go through the car if they do not have enough space to overtake them.

The questionnaire presented at the end of the VR experience was done by using Google's Form service to create free surveys for personal use. This conveniently organises all answers and makes it possible to export them to a CSV file or even to a Google's Spreadsheet page, where it is possible to analyse the data. The form is available at the appendix A.2.

The survey is divided into two different segments. The first one contains control questions regarding the experiment as a whole, such as the order of execution of experiment with audio, how realistic the feeling and experience of the city were, as well as the actions that happened. The first question listed is to evaluate if any cross-over effect happened for using a Within-Subject research method. The others test if any city element or action during the test impaired or damaged the

realism levels of the scene or if it was the audio introduced. These will be compared later to the answers regarding the audio experience. This also includes a specific control question targeting the validation of the questionnaire, as if the user has not noticed any difference between the phases, this means that the user has completely disregarded the audio available or was not paying attention at all during the audio run.

If the user successfully answered that there were clear differences between each of the runs, it is redirected to a second group of questions. These contain most of the questions selected at the subsection 3.2. This will focus on evaluating the attention levels regarding the identification and respective behaviour to audio events. Specific events to test target ambience elements, such as the existence of animals (expected result is seagulls) or the existence of certain elements like the ambulance and to specify how many types could be distinguishable either by vision and/or by hearing (correct result is two for both). The opposite can also to test what element produced a sound. This was used to determine if the participants know what object played the alarm event (the answer is yellow Volkswagen. Yellow car is also acceptable). The last two questions were evaluation questions regarding the overall experience with audio to check how well it improved the current scenario and to check if the user felt any difference in his behaviour during the audio run. Finally, the last input on the survey is a comment section filled by the researcher to write details about the experiment and also the comments mentioned by the participant.

4.4 Results and Discussion

For this experience was defined as a set of independent and dependent variables to study. The independent variables comprehend the number and the type of components and events existent on the Unity scene, as well as the inputs the user provides for controlling the car. The dependent variables are the realism level of the scene and the user's perception and attention to the audio events. Both dependent variables are subjective and require some analysis of the context and the experiment and do not completely rely on the data obtained.

In total, twenty-six different people participated in this study, all of them belonging to the age group between eighteen and twenty-four, being only twenty-three percent of them female. Only two out of the twenty-six participants do not own a drivers license but have some experience with driving, either by using gaming wheels or by playing video games. On average, it took twenty to thirty minutes to fully complete the experiment. This included explaining the research, executing it and answering the questionnaire. Two people had all of their data compromised, one was invalidated due to not finishing the experiment and another due to failing the control question regarding the difference between both phases. Out of the twenty-four valid ones, thirteen started the experience with audio and the other eleven ones only experienced it on the second run.

Before the data analysis from the questionnaire, it is necessary to first analyse the obtained log data to validate certain events. This was generated on each run during a certain time gap, and at the end of the run to ensure every event is recorded. This outputs to a text file named after the

number of the participant. The figure 4.11 represents an example of the structure of the originated log files.

```

Collided Skoda Capsule --- 17:26:26 --- (127.7, 5.9, 352.3) --- (126.7, 6.1, 356.9)
-----
Collided Skoda Capsule --- 17:26:40 --- (137.1, 5.9, 352.0) --- (132.6, 6.1, 353.2)
-----
Audio ambulance medium played --- 17:27:00 --- (216.4, 6.6, 239.0) --- (219.4, 6.6, 258.1)
-----
Audio ambulance medium played --- 17:27:43 --- (216.4, 6.6, 239.0) --- (222.7, 6.7, 255.7)
-----
Collided Golf Capsule --- 17:28:17 --- (-2.4, 9.5, 208.5) --- (-6.3, 9.8, 211.0)
-----
Audio ambulance high played --- 17:28:30 --- (26.5, 9.6, 172.3) --- (19.8, 9.7, 183.5)
-----

```

Figure 4.11: Log file snippet example

Each line has information of a specific audio event played. First the name of the audio event plus the name in case of collision. Second contains the timestamp, followed by the position of the audio source and the player's position. To validate the data gathered by the questionnaire, it is necessary to check if all audio events occur at least once to not constraint the user's experience. For this, a script was done to check if all files contained at least one of each events and to create an average for every audio trigger to further analyse it. In case of having any missing event, the run is considered invalid and the data of said user is ignored.

All of the ambience results averaged one per run, with the exception of one of the main ambiences due to retransitioning from the busy people ambience. On the figure 4.10 the mentioned busy ambience plays on the blue area, so the ambience associated with the yellow zone will replay once, counting twice. As for the events, every event played at least once. Highlights for the alarm event, which averaged more than five times per run and each of the ambulances averaged just above three times. Also, it was verified that no user missed any audio event, so everyone experienced all available events. This means that, despite answering negatively to hearing to a certain event, this will not be thanks to the non-existence of such.

The most repeated event was the collision with objects or pedestrians. In total, there were 548 collisions among twenty-four participants. On average, there were twelve collisions per person on the audio run and eleven on the audioless. The difference between both cases is almost irrelevant as the percentage of collisions on the audio phases is 52 percent of the total collisions, which is almost the same as its counterpart. This might have happened due to having two more experiments in total where the participants first played with headphones against the eleven total second audio runs. Ignoring the audio order and by analysing if the order of the experiment had any impact on the driving behaviour, it comes also to an inconclusive result. Only 53 percent of total collisions

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happened in the second run, which is almost even, once again. Before starting the experiments, it was expected the opposite to happen as people would need some time to get used to the steering wheel to drive the car so they would hit more times. But, after analysing peoples driving skills and by the results, people had trouble driving initially, but get more comfortable throughout the time. So, it is possible that participants are more prone to making more mistakes along the path when relaxed, colliding more with the environment, as there is no pressure due to lack of real consequences. To summarise, audio had no clear impact on the driving skills for this experiment.

After validating the user's runs and confirming that every user had equal opportunity to hear all available events, it is now necessary to analyse the questionnaire data. This study will be divided into two distinct groups. One to evaluate the immersion level of the whole experiment and the improvement audio brought to the user experience. The other one is to evaluate data to use as base of the attention model to see if it had any impact on the users and/or if it is representative enough to justify adding a specific rule to the model.

First, it was necessary to fix and standardise all gathered answers to better interpret it. Due to the ambiguity of certain answers and the existence of grammatical misspellings, all of these were corrected into a more unified group representative of all answers. Depending on the answer type and relevance, some answer groups might change to give more detailed information for better understanding of the results.

For user experience related questions, the scale used was a seven point Likert Scale to allow for evaluating how close this was in comparison to real life scenarios. Higher values mean they are closer to the expected and lower means something was out of context or was not realistic enough. The following figures 4.12 and 4.13 represent the answer distributions to the question of how close the feeling of being in a city was and to how relatable the VE situations were to real life ones. The X axis represents the Likert scale vote chosen and the Y axis the total amount answered for that option.

Figure 4.12: Feeling of being in a real city environment

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Figure 4.13: City activity compared to real life scenario

The average results for both questions were 4.56 for 4.12 and 4.76 for 4.13. In spite of being positive results, indicating a good experience felt by the participants, this was highly influenced by the current Archisim vehicles and pedestrian behaviour. Due to their limitations in some key actions like crossing the road, being permanently immovable on some case scenarios and even on other movement bugs related to said city elements, leads to irregular actions by the participant, as well as damaging the perception they have over some core city elements, As commented by the participants, having no direct response or stimuli to the users actions caused some loss of the city feeling. However, this is still a positive review indicating other aspects are what to be expected, such as the visual identity of the city.

Figure 4.14: Impact of the audio run relatively to its counterpart

Figure 4.15: Change in behaviour during the audio phase

The axis represent the same as the previous two questions. By comparing the results to the obtained on the audio experience, it is clear that this had some impact on the users, as seen on the figures 4.14 and 4.15. These represent the distribution of the questions regarding how the introduction of audio impacted its city experience and how it changed the user’s behaviour and perception of their surroundings.

These results are more conclusive in determining how more realistic the immersive experience is with the introduction of audio. Question 4.14 averaged a 5.75 out of 7 and question 4.15 averaged a 6.00. This indicates that the audio events introduced were close to what to be expected and provided an overall good experience on the users, validating the previous selection of audio events. This also upgraded the user knowledge of their surroundings, changing how they perceive the VE and acting accordingly. Improvements suggested to this were related to missing some generic audio events which were missing, like the variation of sirens available and also the traffic diversity of sounds. Again, this was kind of limited to what already existed on the scenario, as well as the limited interactions the Archisim vehicle provided. Also, since some people did not find out why the alarm event happened and found it to be too annoying, they mentioned it being too random and therefore worsening the experience. This was expected to happen to some extent to maintain noise pollution due to the previously mentioned limitations. Summarising, the audio approach seems to be validated by the shown results.

Following up the audio experience is the identification and behaviour evaluation for modelling purposes. First targeted question was relative to what most relevant sound events were recognised during the time on the VE. The results are available on two different figures 4.16 and 4.17.

Most relevant sounds

Figure 4.16: More relevant sounds to the scene

Figure 4.17: More relevant sounds to the scene in groups

As explained previously, there are differences in the set group of audio labels. This is to show what specific components were targeted to improve the relevance of specific events. For example, people talking, seagulls, beaches and school are all elements associated with the city’s ambience, therefore on the figure 4.17, these are joined together. This is to better target a specific type of event on the impact it had. Twenty one out of twenty four people answered positively

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on identifying more elements thanks to the presence of audio, averaging two distinct events per person, as only the ones who had the most impact are the focal point of the question. The most relevant one on the experience was the ambulance audio event, plus ambience, ice cream truck and Archisim vehicles being also on the top relevant sounds. One reason for this is because of how relevant and informative these events provide on a daily basis are, especially for ambulances and cars to detect their presence. The ice cream truck has some impact due to the surprise factor it brings. As for the ambience it is relative to the augmentation it provides to the city soundscape, improving the feeling of being in a city environment. However, when detailing its elements no conclusion comes to a specific place or object responsible for it, as seen by the low number of answers in figure 4.16. This is due to their triviality of information they provide by simply acting as an experience enhancer and not a specific interest source.

Next question was to test if any elements that were only initially identifiable by their respective audio and which ones of these were. Contrary to the last question, this was targeted to all sounds the person remembers listening to and not only the most relevant ones. For this question, it was also analysed not only if the people answered something to this, but also what order they executed the audio phase. This is to test if any cross-over effect happened that lead to a possible bias on the answer, as people who only had audio available on the second run had more time to detect elements. In total, nineteen out of twenty-four people answered with at least one option. Comparing the execution test order obtained balanced results, as there was a disparity of three people, belonging to the first order group. This is not significant enough, being even less significant as there were exactly two extra people belonging to the first order group in total, so the difference of people not answering is almost the same for both groups. The results are available on the following figure 4.18.

Figure 4.18: Exclusive identification of events by sound

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The results for this are not very promising due to the low amount of average on each answer, being only 1.36 per person who answered and 1.08 in total. This leads to believe that audio has not that big of an impact to exclusively provide this kind of information. Which makes sense due to vision having a bigger impact on the driving experience as it is the main attention modality required for driving. This will be discussed more on the rest of this subchapter. The most identified audios were the ambulances and ambience. Ambulances average 47 percent of the answered questions and 37 percent in total. This is relatively good comparing to other elements. One approach for this is that the ambulance as a bigger impact on the context of a city, being it one of the official priority vehicles that can change completely the behaviour of a driver. The ambience as some impact also due to being almost exclusively identified by the audio, as the only real visual impact it has is when the view changes, which is only near the beach. Otherwise, no specific ambience would be identified, other than a generic city.

To test how people identify specific city locations based on the current soundscape, it was asked if the participants could identify one or more areas and the respective soundscape description. Thirteen people (54 percent) positively answered on identifying zones thanks to audio. The distribution of answers is available at the figure 4.19. This shows a different set of results from the usual to show how ambiguous it is on classifying ambience. For some people, ambulances and traffic noise are an example of ambience zone, perhaps due to the agglomerate of events at a local place. By analysing the ambience values, it is possible to see that the most mentioned is the school. People talking is an ambiguous term and is a generic description of the school soundscape, as it is the only possible location to hear voices. In total, eight people (33 percent) correctly felt passing by a school. Comparing to the generic city ambience and beach effects, this makes sense in being more relevant, due to the more dramatic change of soundscape when passing by adding more components and the increase of volume, as opposed to the more calm soundscape.

Despite the ambience events being trivial as an information source and act more like an immersive enhancer, it still provided some intel on elements that otherwise would not be identified. One specific question had the goal of testing how many people could identify seagulls but only six people (twenty-five percent) detected its presence. Nonetheless, despite not being of much relevance to the driving process, some people still managed to identify its presence, just like other ambience elements, but of course at a much lower relevance percentage comparing to other elements like the ambulances, as it will be studied later on.

Figure 4.19: Different detected ambiances

As seen at the figure 4.19, the ice cream truck event was on the group of more irrelevant location ambiances. This can perhaps be explained by the contextualisation it is inserted. Despite being a frequent part of the city soundscape for certain cities, it can change depending on the user experience. Checking the results for the detected out of context city audio events at the figure 4.20 there is a clear voting decision.

Figure 4.20: Out of context city constituents

Nine out of twenty-four people (37.5 percent) classified the ice cream music as being out of place. This was already bound to happen and was introduced precisely to see how people would

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react to a possible out of context unit. The approach for a possible city location classifier did not seem to have any impact, as analysed at the start of this paragraph. To test if it had any impact on the user's behaviour, it will need to move on to the next question regarding user behaviour.

To see if at any time during the experiment, any of the users looked at the audio source either as a stimuli reaction to it or to figure out the sound emitter, the participants could specify all different times they remember having this change of normal behaviour. The next figure 4.21 contains all collected answers.

Figure 4.21: Need to look at audio source to identify it

By reviewing the results of the previous question, only ten different people confirmed that they had moved due to an audio event. The number of times they also moved their heads is very restricted and is limited to an average of 1.5 times per each of these ten people. This does not register repeated times people had to look at said objects because by personal comments and by analysing the user's behaviour through the experiment, it was negligible the number of times people repeated looking at an audio source already experienced, being the only cases relative to the Archisim cars. This indicates that for the selected participants, audio played a bigger role in informing the user rather than forcing any movement to check what it is, as you do not need, most of the time, to move your head to identify where something is coming from and only restrict this movement to get a precise location of the object.

As mentioned on the psychoacoustics section 2.1.1, it is hard to predict with a certain level of detail where the source is. The need to look is higher on more dangerous related events, such as the ambulance and the Archisim cars. This is due to normal driving behaviour where it is common to look at any cars and ambulances whilst driving to check for any sudden movement or activity. All other answered events have a very low amount of mentions, topping at only two. Ice cream event confirms the number of people who identified the political party represented by the disguised ice cream truck and also that it had no special impact on the user's behaviour, despite being an

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out of context audio. Two people mentioned every new one which is false for one people, who could not recognise which city member played the alarm events, as seen on one of the following questions, which technically reduce this event's accuracy. Next question focuses on the attention levels regarding the interaction with ambulances.

To evaluate the impact the ambulances had on the driver's experience, it was questioned how many they could identify, either by sound and vision. The structure of answers organised manages how many ambulances identified discerns the number by diving the answer into two parts. One contains how many types they saw and how many different sounds there was to facilitate this analysis. Both ambulances have the same audio pattern but, as previously stated, one has a higher frequency/pitch. The results are available on the pie chart at figure 4.22.

Half of the participants managed to visually identify both ambulances but only recognised one distinct audio signal. In fact, only 12.5 percent of people managed to identify both variants of the audio signal. An explanation for this is to most people associating the common ambulance pattern to the type of object and subconsciously do not pay attention to existing a variance for the audio signal. This can lead to believe that not so significant changes to an audio clip are usually ignored and automatically identify the object despite said variations.

Figure 4.22: Ambulance identification

In total, eighteen people identified at least one ambulance thanks to the vision. Only five people answered listening to ambulances and not seeing any of them. This seems to consider that audio does, in fact, have some impact in providing information to the users regarding their surroundings while being focused on other actions, instead of relying on vision, in spite of this being the main modality used while driving. Since driving is an intense activity that requires a lot of attention, by providing audio would complement the previous multimodal diagram, adding one more component to provide information about the objects. However, with the introduction of

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a new modality will compel to distribute the attention, as there are more components to be aware of. This is also one probable reason as to why there are only three people who recognised the two different audio signals. However, no clear conclusions as to how much audio complements vision as a whole, as there are not enough people to take a more assertive conclusion but it can be confirmed that it has some impact on the perception of surroundings.

Another similar test was conducted to check if audio could force people into looking at a determined element and to properly characterise it. This was targeted towards the parked yellow Volkswagen which emitted a loud alarm sound at random times, as already discussed. Eleven out of total participants claimed to know the source of the object, although only seven (29 percent) got the colour and the brand of the car right. The other four failed at the colour but managed to identify the brand and that it was a parked car. This is a very low success rate, despite some people reporting getting scared of the event and consequently changing their attention. This can be justified by the triviality of the audio clip has on the driving basis, not being of much relevance to the driver. This has been a trend on all previous answers, where the alarm event has not been mentioned much, especially on most relevant sounds results at figure 4.16, so people ignored it despite being loud and performing multiple times through the experience.

Out of the seven who got right, only two people agreed that it required looking at the car to acknowledge it. The other five were a mix of guessing and pattern recognition. This is due to the low amount of variety of elements and parked cars there exist and by memorising which elements they pass by. This is somewhat of a cross-over effect which happened on the same experience, as repeated actions seem to lead to a more significant information source other than trying to force people at looking. The multimodal problem brought on previously on the ambulance identification also provides some insight of this, as that the attention levels the user retains for the audio modality is lower due to the different tasks he has to perform, so it seems more frequent to the user recognising something by patterns other than having to perform another new action. However, no real conclusion can come off as once again, there is a very insignificant number of participants who communicated such events.

To summarise the audio attention evaluation, no exact conclusions can be generalised due to not having a representative sample overall, especially for certain cases as seen on the answer report. However, some interesting assumptions can be listed regarding the feedback, either by comments or data obtained, the users have provided.

- Cross-over effect had little to no impact on the research method selected.
- Made possible for an easier recognition of important city elements such as the Ambulance and Archisim cars
- Made the identification of non-existent or not visible components such as the ambience.
- Non-driving elements had little impact on changing the attention the users had while driving. Even if the trivial event is louder than usual, if it proves no little danger to the driver, it is more likely to be ignored.

- Out of context events were easily detectable as such but provide little to no impact on the driving behaviours.
- Little to no extra body movements required to recognise the audio sources available.
- Introduction of a new modality to the already existent multimodal system can complement the drivers surrounding information and remove the need to focus on other aspects, such as needing to always rely on vision to identify objects but makes harder testing certain interactions with a specific component.
- Driving focuses the participant's attention into a selected set of actions making more trivial sounds losing the importance they would have had on other contexts.
- Having a feeling of no real consequences make the users feel more comfortable while driving, resulting in more unrealistic data. This is seen by a large number of collisions and a slight increase with time.

4.5 Classification and Attention Model Integration and Limitations

To first start implementing the classification and attention model proposed, it is required to first remember the proposed architecture presented on the figure 3.8. In order to fully use the python server component, it requires the extraction of information on the Unity project. The context is already being used and sent to other backend servers, such as the Archisim and Pedestrian controllers. Due to the need of running several different programs and projects, being them both servers and Unity, this requires some processing power to smoothly run both programs without losing much efficiency and frames per second. The introduction of the selected CNN using Keras and Tensorflow, as discussed on 3.3, was deemed highly costing in both processing and graphical power, to run at efficient times. This is highly problematic as current hardware constraints will limit and possibly not even be viable the response time to obtain the signal classification results.

As for the perception part of the Unity project, it still requires obtaining the audio from the current agent's point of view. To do this, it is desired to have the current audio signal mix at a certain location. This needs to obtain the same information as the Audio source transmits to the computer's output device. Unity provides a class for this called *Audio Listener* which contains functions that can manipulate the current audio and obtain the current bytes listenable at a particular audio source and also a method called *OnAudioFilterRead* which receives data as bytes from the current audio mix to be able to manipulate it. This at first seems to be useful to use to gather the current mix at any point of the Unity project.

But, this also provided some limitations which could not be handled. Using both suggested methods produced any results in trying to extract the audio mix signal. This at first seemed to be a problem due to the usage of FMOD, which could interfere with how Unity processed Audio. Further tests using only Unity default packages proved to be somewhat true. However, there were still limitations regarding this functionalities as it was possible to manipulate the current mix,

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getting the data was complicated and the only result available was saving the data of the current mix produced by an object, which had attached to it various audio sources. This means that there was no success in obtaining the master audio signal but only a local one. This completely defeated the purpose of using a Classification CNN as there was no final audio file to classify. It was proposed to only do this to the current user by using an external script to record the output directly into a file. Since this was not useful at all as no feedback would be sent to any agents and only to the user itself, plus with the current hardware restrictions on running the Keras server, it was dismissed and proceeded to find an alternative.

The solution for this problem was to have a temporary replica of audio identification and classification inside the Unity project. This would imply having to simulate a hearing radius to limit the maximum distance possible to identify audio events as well as hearing zones of the audio sources. For this, the listener agent was added a spherical trigger zone that would emulate the audible zone of the agent. The audio sources would then emit a new spherical trigger area to represent the possible audio zone. If both collided, it means that the agent could *hear* the audio. Methods were developed to obtain information regarding of what audio event it played and at what intensity is listenable at the player's current position. This virtually tries to create a replica of an audio perception system but, it is too unrealistic due to already predetermining what every event is. The figure 4.23 better demonstrates this implementation.

Figure 4.23: Example of solution implemented

The most external sphere represents the possible hearing radius, whilst the other spheres are audio event related. On the cockpit, visible thanks to the arrows, there are two distinct events. The

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smaller one represents the ambience only listenable by the user and the other the car engine. The last sphere is represented by the alarm event, which is produced by the yellow car. While inside the external hearing sphere or by colliding with another, it will register as a new detected sound and start accounting it as listenable, updating its current status as the object's position changes.

This is where the attention model would come in handy to determine whether if the user could detect the presence of certain audio and determine the source and its location as an attempt to make the experience more realistic for the agents. But, other circumstances lead to the dismissal of said complete implementation.

As the results obtained on the experiment were not considered significant enough to have a clear conclusion on the audio impact, the usage of said data would produce unrealistic behaviour by the agents. This would also require implementing a visual attention model since the most conclusive result was that audio would be a complement to the visual aspect. So the process of identifying and associating the audio signal must be connected by a visual interpretation, otherwise would not make sense to identify an element by not even being on the current field of view.

In spite of said restrictions, methods were created that can still be adapted to use data for object identification, which just requires the introduction of more relevant and representative data. As for now, the user can determine what the audio clip represents but not distinguish which object it was. Once there are more relevant statistics, the function which correlates the audio with the object will be adapted as to determine the audio source if that is the case. However, some changes were done to adapt for some results obtained. Different ambulance events will be perceived as the same, due to the very weak identification of both. The list of listenable audio events was ordered by the intensity of each sound to determine which are closer to the user. This provides a basic attention model allowing the agent to acknowledge the presence of said events, something which could not be fully done before.

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Chapter 5

Conclusions and Future Work

For this final chapter, an overview of all developed work is presented as well as insight into the main accomplishments and conclusions achieved throughout the whole dissertation process. Some suggestions to further develop this work's current state are made, either to improve the already existent content or to implement new methods and/or technologies, which limited some features to be implemented during the execution of this dissertation.

5.1 Dissertation overview and Conclusions

During this project's development, a large variety of topics were introduced to implement a solution for this dissertation's main goal, which ultimately was the study and creation of an audio attention model. Each field of study had some contribution to the current state achieved or presented new information which conditioned or changed the development at the time. To summarise, it will be highlighted some key components that were important and need to be synthesised once again.

- **Audio Perception Replica.** With the study of Psychoacoustics, it was possible to analyse the limitations of the human auditory system due to the sheer complexity of the human anatomy and audio processing. One particular difficult activity to analyse is the sound localisation as there are a lot of variants that change our perception of sound, with the two main cues being Interaural time and Interaural level differences. Since conventional audio systems, such as stereo, do not consider the human anatomy, this causes a weak realistic reproduction. With the study of 3D Audio and Binaural system, it was possible to implement a solution which solved these problems. Using Resonance Audio, it was possible to create a realistic spacial auditory perception field which can adapt to the current number of output channels. This provided a better experience for the VR users as well as allowing for improved perception of sound location on a periphonic level, solving some problems such

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as the Interaural time and level differences as well as the interactions of sound waves with the human body and environment.

- **Audio in Immersive VR Experiences.** By reproducing a more realistic auditory experience, the realism level increase and therefore improve the user's experience. However, this is directly dependent on the audio selected and the given context of the VE. By studying the soundscape to replicate, like the city for this dissertation context, it was possible to recreate said sound experience and improve already existent immersive VE.
- **Audio Classification NN.** Despite existing several methods for audio classification, it still is not very accurate but it produces good generic results. To improve its accuracy requires some result interpretation which can vary depending on the context. No real impact on the usage of attention models, which proposed an improvement for said classification results, can be made due to heavy processing of the CNN selected as well as restrictions with the Unity software for live audio extraction for multiple audio listeners.
- **Research methods** Using Within-Subject research method and Grounded theory proved to be useful to evaluate the audio realism level of the scene, how well it fitted the scene as well as analyse data for testing the attention levels and the audio perception throughout the experience. However, to have conclusive results, a more representative sample is needed to produce usable data.
- **Audio Attention.** Audio attention is hard to study, not only due to the human anatomy problems but also because there is no direct stimuli response other than the head and eye movement. Although the proposed study method proved useful, having a new modality introduced on a system increases the attention span the user can have. This makes relying on a specific modality more complicated and hard to study reactions to it. For this context, since driving requires a lot of attention regarding the actions and vision to perform it, audio decreases the need for relying on them and introduces a new information source. Results obtained on the experiment show that the only big impact audio had on the behaviour was to ambulances due to the high importance this has on a daily basis. As audio seems to complement the vision on informing of the surrounding city elements, some behaviour changes were noticed but were the only kind of relevant for the ambulance, for the mentioned reasons. However, it managed to make a better understanding of other trivial elements not once identifiable such as the ambience.

5.2 Future Work

For further development of this project, some recommendations to future usage are left to improve this dissertation's approach and to solve some limitations that came up during this work's progress.

Since the proposed CNN required some graphical and processing power, adding to the fact that the Unity project and already existent backend controllers also require a lot of computational

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resources, using a more high-end computer with better processing units and a good dedicated graphics card would improve the system's performance and maybe make it viable to use and perhaps manage to produce real-time classification results of audio signals.

A better focus on the classification of certain audio signals is also required to improve the results. This can possibly be solved by using the attention model of the proposed CNN but can also be adjusted to this context. By using a more targeted light dataset with only somewhat relevant audio labels to this and having a more balanced dataset with more complete data for low labeled events, adding more audio samples for events with low coverage on the dataset, this could make the results more clear for this context only.

After this, a better study of Unity's framework and documentation is needed to see if there is a way to extract audio from any audio listener available. Then, repeat the process for middleware plugins such as FMOD to not limit the choice of audio integration to rely only on the default available methods on Unity. This makes possible the implementation of the desired architecture planned.

There is still room for improvement regarding the current scenario experienced by the users. One downside it offers is the unrealistic actions of the pedestrians and Archisim vehicles, which was a huge factor in the participant's opinion and results when evaluating the scene's realism levels. The Soundscape and the diversity of elements on the city can also be updated and upgraded to better increase the realism levels and audio impact on the users. By adding more variety of components and audio events will remove some feelings of repetitiveness while immersed and also avoid having more chances of pattern creation and generating bias towards the experiments. To also improve the audio quality and realism, studies regarding the acoustics of the city can be done to recreate on the scene and then configure the reverberations and wave reflections in Google's Resonance prefabs.

To improve the research method use and gather usable data for an attention model, a more representative number of people is needed to get more conclusive results. If possible, the usage of Between-Subject design, making users only experiment one of the runs, would provide better and more conclusive results by removing any possible Cross-Over effect, even if little or not significant. This would also enable the evaluation of both scenarios to better evaluate the impact of audio by using other statistical comparisons such as Kendall correlations.

Implementing or using a visual attention model to comprehend where users look at while driving could complement these results and improve the model's efficiency. As with the introduction of a new modality decreases the need to use the others, it is strongly suggested to see how vision has been affected as a whole.

Finally, once valid data is obtained, the implemented solution can be updated with it to perform the identification and actions the agent should have, since this has been disabled due to the lack of valid data.

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Appendix A

Appendix

A.1 Consent Declaration

The following document is based on the Declaration of Helsinki, which is a statement of ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects, including research on identifiable human material and data. This was given to every participant to read before doing the experiment and promptly signed in case of agreement. The document is in Portuguese due to the available target audience.

DECLARAÇÃO DE CONSENTIMENTO

(Baseada na declaração de Helsínquia)

No âmbito da realização da tese de Mestrado Integrado em Engenharia Informática da Faculdade de Engenharia da Universidade do Porto, intitulada **Audio-based attention modelling in virtual reality environments**, realizada pelo estudante **João Henrique Catarino Cardoso Loureiro**, orientada pelo Prof. João Jacob e sob a co-orientação do Prof. Eduardo Magalhães, eu abaixo assinado, declaro que compreendi a explicação que me foi fornecida acerca do estudo em que irei participar, nomeadamente o carácter voluntário dessa participação, tendo-me sido dada a oportunidade de fazer as perguntas que julguei necessárias.

Tomei conhecimento de que a informação ou explicação que me foi prestada versou os objectivos, os métodos, o eventual desconforto e a ausência de riscos para a minha saúde, e que será assegurada a máxima confidencialidade dos dados.

Explicaram-me, ainda, que poderei abandonar o estudo em qualquer momento, sem que daí advenham quaisquer desvantagens.

Por isso, consinto participar no estudo e na recolha de dados necessários, respondendo a todas as questões propostas.

Porto, ____ de _____ de 2019

(Participante ou seu representante)

A.2 Questionnaire Form

The following document is a copy of the Google Forms document that all participants answered at the end of the experiment in order to collect data regarding the experiment previously done. Like the Consent Declaration, this is also in Portuguese. This is separated in three different phases, the first one contains generic control questions and the second one is to evaluate the perception level of the users and is only answered in case the user passed the previous control question. The last one contains all answers to both parts of the questionnaire. The header for each column represents the order the question that appears on the form.

Estudo acerca de Impacto do áudio na percepção e reação de utilizadores

Questionario a ser respondido após a execução da experiência em Realidade Virtual

* Required

Ordem pela qual efetuou a experiência *

1º ronda com áudio

2ª ronda com áudio

Classifique a sensação que obteve durante a experiência de estar numa cidade *

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

nada muito perto da realidade

Sentiu durante a experiência, que se encontrou em situações semelhantes à vida real? *

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

em tempo algum durante muito tempo

Notou diferença entre ambas as experiências? *

sim

não

NEXT

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Google Forms

Estudo acerca de Impacto do áudio na percepção e reação de utilizadores

* Required

Estudo acerca de Impacto do áudio na percepção e reação de utilizadores

Questões sobre a experiência auditiva do utilizador

Conseguiu identificar mais elementos da cidade através do áudio ? *

- Sim
- Não

Se sim quais foram os mais relevantes.

Your answer

Existiu algum elemento da cidade que foi indetectável exclusivamente pelo som emitido? *

Sim

Não

Se sim quais.

Your answer

Houve algum elemento que tenha detetado que se encontrava fora de contexto? *

Sim

Não

Se sim quais.

Your answer

Necessitou de olhar para poder perceber de onde é que veio determinado som ou para determinar o objeto que o emitia? *

Sim

Não

Se sim qual(quais).

Your answer

Conseguiu identificar qual elemento da cidade emitia o som do alarme? *

Sim

Não

Se sim qual era a cor da fonte sonora

Your answer

Que tipo(s) de ambulância(s) existem? Bastou ouvir para o determinar ou foi necessário recorrer sempre à visão para o conseguir distinguir? *

Your answer

Conseguiu identificar presença de animais? Se sim quando é que foi mais prevalente

Your answer

Consegui identificar diferentes partes da cidade através do som ambiente? *

Sim

Não

Se sim dê um ou dois exemplos de sons ambiente

Your answer

Qual o impacto que o ambiente com som teve em si relativamente à percepção do ambiente face ao outro cenário? *

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

nenhum, ambas são iguais superior, consegui detetar novos elementos

Notou diferença no seu comportamento no ambiente sonificado em relação ao outro cenário? *

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

igual diferente

notas do João

Your answer

BACK

SUBMIT

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Timestamp	Question 1	Question 2	Question 3	Question 4	Question 5
27/05/2019 17:55:43	1º ronda com áudio	3	6	sim	Sim
27/05/2019 23:46:38	2ª ronda com áudio	5	6	sim	Sim
28/05/2019 00:29:19	2ª ronda com áudio	4	6	sim	Sim
28/05/2019 21:18:00	1º ronda com áudio	3	1	sim	Sim
28/05/2019 21:53:46	1º ronda com áudio	4	5	sim	Não
29/05/2019 17:01:37	2ª ronda com áudio	5	4	sim	Sim
29/05/2019 17:32:38	2ª ronda com áudio	5	5	sim	Sim
29/05/2019 18:35:24	1º ronda com áudio	4	2	sim	Sim
29/05/2019 19:05:30	1º ronda com áudio	5	6	sim	Sim
29/05/2019 20:44:53	2ª ronda com áudio	6	6	sim	Sim
30/05/2019 18:02:52	1º ronda com áudio	6	4	sim	Sim
30/05/2019 18:31:25	2ª ronda com áudio	4	5	sim	Sim
31/05/2019 15:35:36	1º ronda com áudio	2	1	sim	Sim
31/05/2019 16:03:41	1º ronda com áudio	5	6	sim	Sim
31/05/2019 16:32:48	2ª ronda com áudio	3	6	sim	Sim
31/05/2019 18:06:56	2ª ronda com áudio	5	5	sim	Sim
02/06/2019 01:30:21	1º ronda com áudio	5	6	sim	Sim
02/06/2019 23:52:38	2ª ronda com áudio	5	4	sim	Sim
03/06/2019 15:40:03	1º ronda com áudio	5	5	sim	Não
03/06/2019 17:46:30	1º ronda com áudio	5	6	sim	Sim
03/06/2019 21:55:12	2ª ronda com áudio	4	5	sim	Sim
04/06/2019 03:28:42	1º ronda com áudio	6	5	sim	Sim
04/06/2019 16:06:35	1º ronda com áudio	5	5	sim	Sim
04/06/2019 17:00:29	2ª ronda com áudio	5	3	não	
04/06/2019 17:24:28	1º ronda com áudio	5	6	sim	Não

Question 6

ambulância, alarmes, peões, colisões

carrinha dos gelados, algumas ambulâncias, gaivotas

gaivotas, carrinha dos gelados, carros

ambulâncias e outros carros

carrinha dos gelados, ambulâncias

outros carros, pessoas, ambulâncias

colisões

ambulâncias, escola

carrinha de gelados

carrinha dos gelados

o ambiente no geral, e a velocidade do cockpit

ambulâncias, carrinha dos gelados e alarmes

motores dos carros

colisões, ambulâncias e carrinha dos gelados

ambulâncias, outros carros e estado do cockpit

carros, ambiente, ambulâncias e alarmes

carros

alarmes, ambulâncias, colisões

na ronda sem áudio, tornou-se quase impossível a perceção das ambulâncias

escola, ambulâncias, colisões

pessoas a falar, motor do cockpit, ambulâncias, carros, carrinha dos gelados , praia porque ouvi o som da maresia

carros

Question 7	Question 8	Question 9	Question 10	Question 11
Sim	ambulâncias, colisões com veiculos	Sim	música dos gelados	Sim
Sim	carrinha dos gelados e gaivotas	Não		Não
Sim	carros	Sim	Carrinha dos gelados	Sim
Sim	ambulância	Não		Não
Sim	ambulância, alarme	Sim	Carrinha gelados	Não
Sim	carrinha dos gelados	Não		Sim
Sim	pessoas	Não		Não
Sim	colisões	Sim	alarme	Sim
Sim	ambulâncias	Não		Não
Sim	cockpit e carros	Não		Não
Não		Não		Não
Não		Não		Não
Sim	ambulâncias	Sim	alarme, carrinha do gelados	Sim
Não		Sim	carrinha dos gelados	Não
Sim	ambulâncias	Não		Sim
Sim	ambiente	Não		Não
Sim	carrinha de gelados e ambiente	Sim	carrinha de gelados	Não
Não		Sim	carrinha dos gelados	Não
Sim	Carrinha de gelados	Sim	Carrinha de gelados	Sim
Sim	ambulância	Sim	um peão voador	Sim
Sim	ambulância na rotunda, pessoas	Sim	escola, alarmes e ambulâncias	Sim
Sim	carros e pessoas	Sim	coisas a levitar	Sim
Não		Não		Não
Sim	ambulância	Sim	carrinha dos gelados	Não

Question 12	Question 13	Question 14
Carro com música dos gelados	Não	
	Não	
alarme, pessoas e carros	Sim	amarelo
	Sim	azul
	Sim	amarelo
carrinha dos gelados	Sim	Volkswagen
	Não	
Todos	Não	
	Não	
	Não	
	Não	
ambulâncias	Não	
	Sim	amarelo
Todos	Sim	Amarelo
	Sim	Carro amarelo
	Não	
	Sim	amarelo
Colisões	Sim	Carros Amarelos
ambulância	Sim	ambulância inem
para os carros nas colisões e ambulância	Não	
ambulância	Sim	fiquei na dúvida se era uma ambulância
	Não	
	Não	

Question 15	Question 16	Question 17
Não consegui visualizar nenhuma, só ouvi	Não	Sim
2, só visão	gaivotas	Não
2, ambas maneiras	gaivotas, a beira da carrinha vermelha	Sim
2, só visão	não	Não
2, só visão	não	Não
2, só visão	Não	Sim
2, só visão	não	Não
Não consegui ver nenhuma, só ouvi	Não.	Não
2, só visão	não	Sim
2, só audição	não	Não
Não vi nenhuma, só ouvi	não	Não
2, só visão	não	Sim
1, só visão	não	Sim
	0 não	Sim
1, só visão	Não	Sim
2, só visão	Gaivotas	Sim
2, só visão	gaivotas	Sim
2, só visão	não	Não
2 só visão	gaivotas	Sim
1, só visão	não	Não
2, só visão	gaivotas	Sim
Não consegui ver nenhuma, só ouvi	Não	Sim
2, ambas maneiras	não	Não
1, só visão	não	Não

Question 18	Question 19	Question 20
Musica dos gelados vs alarmes e ambulâncias	7	6
	6	7
o usual som da gaivota e o som da escola	6	6
	4	7
	5	7
ambiente, carrinha dos gelados	6	5
	7	1
	4	4
Escola	6	7
	7	7
	7	7
praia	6	7
carrinha dos gelados	6	7
carros, pessoas	6	6
Escola	7	7
Perto da escola	7	6
escola, praia e ambiente	6	7
	5	5
Sons de carros, sons de pessoas, ambiente de fundo	6	6
	7	3
ambiente da escola, o ambiente da cidade	4	5
som do mar aka praia	6	7
	3	7
	4	7